

A taxonomy of Nina Lee's Kew and Kewbello

Lemuria¹

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Abstract

The Kew dress, released in August 2017, is one of the earliest patterns from the British pattern label Nina Lee, founded in March 2017 by Nina Chang-Smith. It features three bodice options, a cold-shoulder (a trend at the time of release), a sleeveless sundress, and sleeved tea dress. The later Kewbello combined the bodice of the Kew with her Portobello trousers design. The Kew and Kewbello, collectively, are an example of how the LCT-01's hybrid phylogenetic-phenetic methodology results in the polyphyletic classification of sewing patterns based on their available design options, and the phylogenetic classification of individual design options. We describe 47 species of Kew dresses for the first time publicly, refining the original findings on our internal MediaWiki site.

Table of contents

1	Background	4
1.1	Nina Chang-Smith	4
1.2	Nina Lee	4
1.3	LCT-01	4
1.3.1	Focus	4
1.3.2	Structure	5
1.3.3	Taxonomic history	5
2	Kew	6
2.1	Trends	6
2.2	Population and distribution	6
2.3	Combination matrix	6
2.4	Bodices	7
2.4.1	Kewoidea	7
2.4.2	Helikewidae	8
2.4.3	Kewthidae	8
2.5	Skirts	8
2.5.1	Kewbello	9
3	Methods	9
3.1	Filmot and YouTube	9
3.2	holotyper tool	10
4	Species descriptions	10
4.1	Genus <i>Florankewia</i>	10
4.1.1	<i>Florankewia libera</i>	10
4.1.2	<i>Florankewia valentina</i>	11
4.2	Genus <i>Helikewabotonia</i>	11
4.2.1	<i>Helikewabotonia lanata</i>	11
4.2.2	<i>Helikewabotonia stadile</i>	12
4.3	Genus <i>Helikewisia</i>	12
4.3.1	<i>Helikewisia aemilia</i>	13
4.3.2	<i>Helikewisia ceciliae</i>	13
4.3.3	<i>Helikewisia erinae</i>	14
4.3.4	<i>Helikewisia irvinae</i>	15
4.3.5	<i>Helikewisia kristinae</i>	15
4.3.6	<i>Helikewisia mariae</i>	17
4.3.7	<i>Helikewisia sarae</i>	17
4.4	Genus <i>Helikewisia</i> subg. <i>Emmae</i>	18
4.4.1	<i>Helikewisia arbor</i>	18
4.4.2	<i>Helikewisia quagga</i>	18
4.5	Genus <i>Helikewplicata</i>	19
4.5.1	<i>Helikewplicata ninae</i>	19
4.6	Genus <i>Kewabotonia</i>	20
4.6.1	<i>Kewabotonia eleanorae</i>	20
4.6.2	<i>Kewabotonia elsae</i>	20
4.6.3	<i>Kewabotonia nuptirachaelae</i>	20
4.6.4	<i>Kewabotonia sarae</i>	21
4.6.5	<i>Kewabotonia zingibera</i>	22
4.7	Genus <i>Kewasalia</i>	22
4.7.1	<i>Kewasalia pimsia</i>	22
4.8	Genus <i>Kewisia</i>	23
4.8.1	<i>Kewisia bernicae</i>	23

4.8.2	<i>Kewisia evae</i>	24
4.8.3	<i>Kewisia fionae</i>	24
4.8.4	<i>Kewisia genyae</i>	25
4.8.5	<i>Kewisia kristinae</i>	25
4.8.6	<i>Kewisia latae</i>	27
4.8.7	<i>Kewisia lizae</i>	27
4.8.8	<i>Kewisia mariae</i>	29
4.8.9	<i>Kewisia modistaflora</i>	31
4.8.10	<i>Kewisia modistarubera</i>	31
4.8.11	<i>Kewisia rachaelae</i>	31
4.8.12	<i>Kewisia reginarunae</i>	33
4.8.13	<i>Kewisia sarae</i>	35
4.9	Genus <i>Kewpepla</i>	35
4.9.1	<i>Kewpepla lornae</i>	35
4.9.2	<i>Kewpepla lornaebis</i>	36
4.9.3	<i>Kewpepla mariae</i>	36
4.10	Genus <i>Kewthea</i>	37
4.10.1	<i>Kewthea chantellae</i>	37
4.10.2	<i>Kewthea evae</i>	38
4.10.3	<i>Kewthea lornae</i>	39
4.10.4	<i>Kewthea lornoblae</i>	40
4.10.5	<i>Kewthea luscinia</i>	40
4.10.6	<i>Kewthea modistaflora</i>	41
4.11	Genus <i>Kewthicata</i>	42
4.11.1	<i>Kewthicata juliae</i>	42
4.12	Genus <i>Trunkewia</i>	42
4.12.1	<i>Trunkewia ninae</i>	42
4.13	Genus <i>Trunkewia</i> subg. <i>Illecebrosus</i>	43
4.13.1	<i>Trunkewia rosacrania</i>	43
4.13.2	<i>Trunkewia rubera</i>	43
4.13.3	<i>Trunkewia viridis</i>	44
5	General remarks	44
5.1	Lorna Rothery	44
5.2	Type specimen naming	44
5.3	Per-site archival considerations	44
5.4	Long-term name disambiguation	44
6	Identification key	45
7	Appendix	45
7.1	Person abbreviations	45
7.1.1	Botanical abbreviations	46
7.2	Image specimen list	46
7.3	Acknowledgements	47
7.4	Information	47
7.5	yt-dlp provenance for <i>Kewisia kristinae</i>	48

1 Background

In January 2016, Jessica Bain, at the University of Leicester’s Department of Media and Communication, wrote that the traditional practice of home sewing, specifically dressmaking, was experiencing a revival (Bain 2016). Her paper also quoted some of the sewists we have studied as part of our taxonomy work; such as Marie Koupparis of *A Stitching Odyssey*, and Tilly Walnes of *Tilly and the Buttons*. At the time, the BBC’s *Great British Sewing Bee* had just finished its third season. Not only that, bloggers and Twitter users were building their own community, one that Bain describes as “digital dressmakers”.

Many of these blogs are now the primary source material for significant parts of the LCT-01’s British sewing pattern taxonomy work. Though Bain (2016) was written nearly one year and eight months before the release of the Kew dress, blogging culture was still strong and remained so on the Kew’s release day. While in 2026, many sewists only publish their work to Instagram, blogs still exist, and old ones remain accessible and readable. Link rot has taken its toll, but the Internet Archive has prevented most of the damage.

1.1 Nina Chang-Smith

Perhaps part of the revival that Bain described, in March 2017, Nina Chang-Smith, known at the time as just Nina Chang¹, a British designer, launched her pattern label, Nina Lee, in London (N. Chang 2017)². We again emphasize that special care must be taken to avoid conflating Nina Lee, the brand; with Nina Chang-Smith, the person.

Chang-Smith learned basic sewing in childhood from her mother. She began dressmaking in earnest in her middle teenage years; at 14, she sewed her first garment, a lilac gingham sundress with an empire line waist and puffy sleeves (Svetvilas and Chang-Smith 2023).

In November 2021, she moved to the San Francisco Bay Area, due to her husband’s employment. As a result, she discontinued physical printed patterns and now exclusively sells PDFs. (Svetvilas and Chang-Smith 2023).

1.2 Nina Lee

Since the launch of Nina Lee in 2017, Chang-Smith has released ~22 designs. These are named for places in London (e.g. Kew, Bakerloo, Camden, Southbank, Mayfair), with more recent patterns drawing from California (e.g. Carmel, Mariposa). They are sold as digital

PDFs. Physical patterns remain available, but are becoming rarer as the Post-Californian period progresses.³

Chang-Smith’s patterns range from UK sizes 6–28; she sells them in sets of sizes 6–20 and 16–28. She drafts with a height of 165 cm (5 ft 5 in) and a B cup (system unknown). The patterns typically include a 1.5 cm (5/8 in) seam allowance.

1.3 LCT-01

1.3.1 Focus

Though the LCT-01’s scope is vast, encompassing nearly all clothing, and possibly accessories (pending internal considerations and debates), much of its work has focused on sewing pattern labels.

Numerous factors make the blogs written by sewists, part of an indie home sewing culture primarily concentrated in the Western world⁴, exceptionally digestible primary material for the LCT-01. Photographs from multiple angles provide views of the garment, allowing a taxonomist with a good eye to identify features not documented in the text. Their observations can then be synthesized with the text itself, which describes alterations, life stories, and other morphological changes made to fit its wearer, such as divergences from the pattern, that would require a taxonomist to physically inspect the specimen (which is infeasible ethically and practically).

The sewing pattern itself, mostly in PDF format, can be thought of as the last universal common ancestor of its taxon (Lemuria 2026) and as the *bauplan* (body plan) of its child taxa. When a sewist creates a garment from a pattern, a phylogenetic link emerges between the pattern and the garment, significantly more traceable and certain than biological taxa, which can only be hypothesized.

Major entities that the LCT-01 has covered and has yet to publish taxonomic treatments of include labels such as Nina Lee (the main focus of this article), *By Hand London*, and *Tilly and the Buttons*. Persons include Tilly Walnes (the owner of *Tilly and the Buttons*); Elisalex de Castro Peake (now known as Elisalex Jewell) and Charlotte Hintzen (though she has since left), the founders of *By Hand London*; and the focus of this article, Nina Chang-Smith and her Nina Lee label—though this paper discusses her Kew dress, and Kewbello trousers, some 20 patterns remain to be taxonomized.

¹Her maiden name; she married in June 2019 (Chang-Smith 2020; S. Chang 2019).

²Chang-Smith has since taken down her old blog, but the post is still available on the Wayback Machine. It does not link to the specific blog post, but to the homepage where the post in question is embedded.

³In the history of Nina Chang-Smith, the Post-Californian is the current period, that started on November 1, 2021.

⁴We are aware of Japanese indie sewing culture; however, our lead author only understands English and Tagalog.

1.3.2 Structure

We present an abridged version of the LCT-01's high level structure, only including the taxa relevant to the Kew dresses at hand. A full graph is presented in Figure 1; and here we present basic descriptions of the high level taxa for context, as we have yet to publish more detailed descriptions in the *Journal*.

Domain Vestimentia is the root of the taxonomy. From Latin *vestimentum* (“clothing”), while its definitions are fuzzy, it encompasses garments worn on the human body, excluding standalone accessories.

Kingdom Abtruncusa, from Latin *ab* “down from” + *truncusa* “torso”, encompasses dresses and tops, and in general, any garment worn on the human torso.

Phylum Scapunatoria, from Latin *scapula* “shoulder” + *denudator* “denude, expose”, encompasses garments that expose one or more shoulders.

Class Umerostentida, from Latin *umerus* “shoulder” + *ostenta* “expose”, encompasses garments that have a sleeve lateral to the upper arm while exposing at least one shoulder.

Subclass Bilourida, from Latin *bi-* “two” + Greek *lourida* “strap”, encompasses garments that have bilateral single straps; i.e one strap on each side of the body.

Order Biligamentum, from Latin *bi-* “two” + *ligamentum*, encompasses dresses with bilateral single straps. A dress here is defined as terminating inferior to the pelvic area.

Suborder Biligabotonia, from its parent Biligamentum and Latin *botonia* “button”, encompasses dresses with a ventral medial button row.

Superfamily Kewoidea: See Section 2.4.1.

Subphylum Scapamanica, from its parent Scapunatoria, combined with Greek *a-* “no” + Latin *manica* “sleeve”, encompasses sleeveless garments that expose the shoulder.

Class Helistola, from Greek *helios* “sun” + Latin *stola* “dress”, encompasses sundresses; sleeveless garments that expose the shoulder and have slightly thick straps.

Order Helinina, from Helistola + Nina’s name, encompasses sundresses made from Nina Lee patterns.

1.3.3 Taxonomic history

Lemuria discovered the Kew dress through a 2017 video by the American YouTuber and vlogger Kristin Lehrer, known online as Voolenvine (see Lehrer (2018c)). In the video, she wore a Kew dress, and in the description included a link to Nina Lee’s website for the pattern. This Kew dress is now known as *Kewisia kristinae* Lemuria, 2026.

Family Helikewidae: See Section 2.4.2.

Phylum Manubristenta, from Latin *manubrium* “handle”, the name for the top part of the sternum (breastbone), and *ostenta* “expose”, encompasses garments whose necklines are low enough to expose the skin above the manubrium, slightly inferior to the bottom of the neck.

Class Vecostola, from *ve* “V” + Latin *collum* “neck” + *stola* “dress”, encompasses garments with a V-neck.

Order Vecobotonia, from Vecobotonia + Latin *botonia* “button”, encompasses garments with a ventral medial button row.

Family Kewthidae: See Section 2.4.3.

Clade Subpelvia: Directly below Vestimentia, the clade Subpelvia encompasses multiple kingdoms that encompass clothing below the pelvic region.

Kingdom Suprapatella, from Latin *supra-* “above” + *patella* “knee”, encompasses garments that start at or below the pelvis, but above the knee.

Phylum Castula, from Latin *castula*, encompasses skirts, garments that originate from the pelvis and only have a single “tube” that covers the human body, as opposed to trousers, shorts, or other garments with two “tubes” that cover each leg individually.

Class Botonicasida, from Latin *botonia* + *-casida*, suffix for skirt classes, encompasses skirts with a button row.

Subclass Ventracasidna, from *ventral* + *-casidna*, suffix for skirt subclasses, encompasses skirts with a ventral button row.

Order Ventracasales, from *ventral* + *-casales*, suffix for skirt orders, encompasses skirts where the ventral button row is positioned medially.

Family Kewcasaceae: See Section 2.5.

Family Portobellidae, *incertae sedis* in Suprapatella, encompasses the Portobello trousers by Nina Lee. It is often sewn as a standalone garment, but it has been incorporated into the Kew numerous times, and thus falls within the scope of this paper.

Though the LCT-01 was developed in September 2025, it was “dormant” at the time he first saw Lehrer’s video. He began another period of activity regarding the taxonomy in January 2026; the earliest edits on his internal MediaWiki site, the Lemuria Wiki, pertaining to the Kew, specifically *K. kristinae*, date back to the end of January.

Throughout February and early March, Lemuria contin-

Figure 1: An expanded polyphyletic tree of the Kew dresses.

ued taxonomizing sewing patterns, including the Kew. In mid-March, he established *Lemuria's (Informal) Journal of Clothing Taxonomy* (LICT) as a citizen science/gray literature journal to share his findings.

As of March 16, 2026, the LCT-01 encompasses some 250 species and 70 genera.

2 Kew

The Kew dress, released in August 2017, is the fourth pattern from Nina Lee. Chang-Smith describes the Kew as “feminine, elegant and stylish” and inspired by “the delights of British summertime” in her 2017 Instagram post announcing its release (Chang-Smith 2017b).

2.1 Trends

The cold shoulder, which the Kewoidea offers, was a major trend around 2017. This can be inferred from the temporal range of the Kewoidea, which clusters mostly around the late 2010s. Two outliers exist; *Kewisia berniceae*, sewn in April 2020 (Bernice 2020); see Section 4.8.1, and *Kewabotonia elsa* (sewn 2021; see Section 4.6.2). However, in general, the cold shoulder has fallen out of trend; by 2026, the year this paper was written, it has certainly done so. The fashion cycle may eventually revive the cold shoulder trend, but its future trajectory is unpredictable.

The core characteristics of the tea dress and the sundress variant, specifically their strap and sleeve configurations,

are less vulnerable to changing trends; the continued range of the Kewthidae towards 2025 is seen in *Kewthea lornae*, Section 4.10.3.

2.2 Population and distribution

So far, the Kew dresses cluster primarily in the United Kingdom, the source of the pattern, and to a lesser extent, in the United States. It has been seen in Australia, and in France. The author has yet to determine if the Kew dress has been sewn in the Philippines.

Google results for “nina lee kew dress”, without quotes, claim some 114,000 results, while “nina lee kew” claims 536,000 results.

A more conservative estimate of the total number of Kew dresses is ~3,200 if “nina lee kew dress” is placed in quotes. If we extrapolate from the top ten search results, five of them document individual makes of the Kew, bringing the figure down to ~1,600. One of the results features three makes of a Kew dress, but this is likely to be statistically insignificant. The same makes may also have been reposted onto multiple sites, which further reduces the most-conservative estimate to the hundreds (10e1).

2.3 Combination matrix

The Kew features three bodice variants: a tea dress variant with sleeves; a cold-shoulder variant with straps superior to the scapula and sleeves lateral to the upper arm;

and a sundress variant with the same straps, but without the sleeves.

An expansion pack is also available, which adds two additional skirts, which brings the total to three bodice and three skirt options, which multiply to nine. Chang-Smith claims on the expansion pack that it increases the number of “possible Kew creations” to 12. This claim is true, but slightly counterintuitive. The lack of a bodice entirely is considered the fourth bodice option, and given the ex-

act language of Chang-Smith’s claim, this math is nearly correct. When the options to make a Kewbello, or to make the bodice standalone are added, we reach four bodice options and five skirt options, making for 19 possible creations⁵, showing that Chang-Smith underpromised and overdelivered.

We present a matrix of all possible bodice–bottom⁶ combinations that involve components from either the Kew or Kewbello patterns.

Table 1: A matrix of Kew species. An emdash (—) indicates that a specific skirt–bodice combo has not been described so far, while parentheses indicate that, while the genus name has been coined, no species have been described.

	Sundress	Cold-shoulder	Tea	No bodice
Gathered	<i>Helikewplicata</i>	(<i>Kewplicata</i>)	<i>Kewthicata</i>	<i>Kewplicasa</i>
Straight	<i>Helikewisia</i>	<i>Kewisia</i>	<i>Kewthea</i>	<i>Kewisicasa</i>
Parabola	(<i>Helikewparabola</i>)	(<i>Kewparabola</i>)	—	<i>Kewparacasa</i>
Portobello	(<i>Helikewbellia</i>)	—	(<i>Kewbellothea</i>)	non-Kew
No bottom	<i>Trunkewia</i>	—	<i>Kewpepla</i>	non-Kew

2.4 Bodices

The vast majority of the Kew dresses, with the exception of *Kewabotonia*, feature a ventral medial (center front) button row. Button counts vary with the wearer, from as low as zero (the defining characteristic of *Kewabotonia*) to ~17 (as seen on the line art in Chang-Smith (n.d.)), of which five are on the bodice and the remaining 12 are on the skirt.

The bodices of the Kewoidea and Helikewidae feature bilateral ventral seams that originate around the bust. These seams extend to the parabola skirt (see Section 2.5), as seen in Chang-Smith (n.d.). Laterally, they feature a horizontal seam (as seen in Chang-Smith n.d., and Chang-Smith 2018). The seam extends to the lateral vertical seams (as seen on *K. rachaelae*, *Lateral view 1*).

The characteristics of the Kewthidae are described in Section 2.4.3.

2.4.1 Kewoidea

The cold-shoulder variant encompasses the superfamily Kewoidea. The primary character distinguishing Kewoidea from its closest relative, the sundress bodice (Helikewidae), is the presence of bilateral sleeves. Ventrally, the sleeve attaches to the bodice narrowly before widening. It retains its width until it reaches its dorsal bodice attachment point.

It is further divided into two families, Kewidae and Plesikewidae, which have three genera each. Kewidae is the *sensu stricto* family, consisting of *Kewisia* (straight skirt) and the empty genera *Kewplicata* and *Kewparabola*.

Kewisia is the largest genus in Kewidae, with 13 species: *bernicae* wb. Bernice, 2020, see Section 4.8.1; *evae* wb. Eva, 2018, see Section 4.8.2; *fionae* wb. Parker, 2018, see Section 4.8.3; *genyae* wb. Genya, 2023, see Section 4.8.4; *kristinae* wb. Lehrer (Voolenvine), 2018, see Section 4.8.5; *latae* wb. Vic Broad, 2017, see Section 4.8.6; *lizae* wb. Liz, 2018, see Section 4.8.7; *mariae* wb. Marie, 2018, see Section 4.8.8; *modistaflora* wb. Sally, 2019, see Section 4.8.9; *modistarubera* wb. Sally, 2019, see Section 4.8.10; *rachaelae* wb. Rachael, 2018, see Section 4.8.11; *reginarunae* wb. Alice, 2018, see Section 4.8.12; *sarae* wb. Sarah, 2019, see Section 4.8.13;

Plesikewidae encompasses hacked versions of the Kew, split across two subfamilies, Plesikewinae, distinguished by a skirt, and Kewasalinae, distinguished by trousers. Plesikewinae contains the genera *Florankewia* and *Kewabotonia*, while Kewasalinae contains *Kewasalia*.

Florankewia is home to two species, *F. libera* (described in Section 4.1.1) and *F. valentina* (described in Section 4.1.2), which are two hacks created by Kate Eva. Though the bodice of the By Hand London Flora and the skirt of the By Hand London Anna account for the majority of the dress, *Florankewia* incorporates the off-shoulder sleeves of the Kew.

⁵Not wearing a Kew bodice or a Kew skirt is either full nudity or a non-Kew taxon.

⁶We use the term “bottom” instead of “skirt” as using no skirt or using the Portobello, which are trousers, is also an option.

Kewabotonia is a larger genus, encompassing five species. Four of these descend from a hack by Jen Walker, known as the Gingerthread Girl, as described in Walker (2018). Walker's specific hack of the Kew encompasses *Kewabotonia zingibera* (described in Section 4.6.5), which is also the type species. *Kewabotonia* lacks the ventral medial button row entirely, and has a dorsal medial zipper, which is completely absent among the Kewidae. Chang-Smith herself praised Walker's hack as "the Queen of all the Kew hacks" (2018). The three other species in *Kewabotonia* that descend from Walker's hack are *eleonorae* wb. Eleanor, 2018 (see Section 4.6.1); *sarae* wb. Sarah, 2018 (see Section 4.6.4); and *elsae* wb. Elsa, 2021 (see Section 4.6.2).

The fifth species, *Kewabotonia nuptirachaelae* (described in Section 4.6.3), was sewn by the British sewist Rachael Beaumont in 2018 for one of her bridesmaids, Lizzy (Beaumont 2018a). *Kewabotonia nuptirachaelae* does not explicitly diverge from Walker's hack; Beaumont does not mention it in her blog post. It is distinguished from the rest of genus by its full-circle skirt.

Kewasalia is a monotypic genus, containing *Kewasalia pimisia*. It is attested in Chang-Smith (2018), which describes the garment as a jumpsuit. She credited it to @pimsyfai-destruks, whose Instagram account is no longer available.

2.4.2 Helikewidae

The sundress variant encompasses the family Helikewidae. It is similar to Kewoidea but is sleeveless. Helikewidae is further divided into the subfamilies Helikewinae and Trunkewinae.

Trunkewinae is home to the genus *Trunkewia*. In addition to the first public description of *Trunkewia ninae* wb. Nina, 2018 (described in Section 4.12.1), we describe the new subgenus *Illecebrosus*, and its three species *rosacrania*, see Section 4.13.1; *rubera*, see Section 4.13.2; and *viridis*, see Section 4.13.3. All three were made by @epp.roseberry.couture (Terranova Stéphanie), whose Instagram account is no longer available.

Helikewinae is further divided into two tribes, Helikewbellini and Helikewini.

Helikewbellini (see Section 2.5.1) is monotypic, containing the genus *Helikewbellia*, with no species described at present.

Helikewini is divided into three genera, based on the three skirt options: *Helikewisia*, *Helikewplicata*, and *Helikewparabola*; alongside the new genus *Helikewabotonia*. Like Kewidae, only *Helikewisia* is populated with species.

Helikewisia contains nine species. Directly under it are *aemilia* wb. Emily of L., 2017, see Section 4.3.1; *ceciliae* wb. Cecilia, 2018, see Section 4.3.2; *erinae* wb. Erin.M.,

2021, see Section 4.3.3; *irvinae* wb. Alice.Ir., 2020, see Section 4.3.4; *kristinae* wb. Lehrer, 2018, see Section 4.3.5; *mariae* wb. Maria (W/2026 F1), see Section 4.3.6; and *sarae* wb. Sarah of T., 2019, see Section 4.3.7; and the *Emmae* which contains the remaining two: *arbor* wb. Emma of N., 2019, see Section 4.4.1; and *quagga* wb. Emma of N. and unknown friend, 2019, see Section 4.4.2.

Helikewisia kristinae, Lehrer's first make of the Kew dress, was previously unknown. The specimen was identified while reviewing holotype material for *Kewisia kristinae*. See Section 4.3.5.

We describe the new genus *Helikewabotonia* and its two species: *stadile* wb. Emma of N., 2019, see Section 4.2.2; and *lanata* wb. Joy of B., see Section 4.2.1.

2.4.3 Kewthidae

The tea dress variant encompasses the family Kewthidae, characterized by ruched sleeves that terminate slightly superior to the elbow. It is split into the subfamilies Kewthinae and Kewbellinae. Kewbellinae has no genera, while Kewthinae is divided into three genera: *Kewthea*, the tea dress, with a skirt; *Kewpepla*, the peplum top; and *Kewthicata*, the tea dress, with a gathered skirt.

Kewthea is home to six species: *lornae* wb. Lorna.R., 2020, see Section 4.10.3; *lornoblae* wb. Lorna.R., 2020, see Section 4.10.4; *luscina* wb. Ruth.Pr., 2019, see Section 4.10.5; *modistaflora* wb. Sally of M., 2019, see Section 4.10.6; *evae* wb. Eva, 2018, see Section 4.10.2; and *chantellae* wb. Chantelle, 2018, see Section 4.10.1.

Kewpepla is home to three species: *lornae* wb. Lorna.R., 2020, see Section 4.9.1; *lornaebis* wb. Lorna.R., 2020, see Section 4.9.2; and *mariae* wb. Marie, 2018, see Section 4.9.3.

Lorna Rothery (<https://lornarothery.com/>; abbreviated Lorna.R. in the LCT-01), is the most prolific sewist among the Kewthidae, with four documented specimens.

While rereviewing source material, new species of *Kewthidae* were also discovered. From Sally of M. (2020), we describe the new species *Kewthea modistaflora*. The material was first reviewed while taxonomizing Modista Sewing's *Kewisia* spp., but at the time the genus *Kewthea* had not been described, and was thus omitted.

We also describe the new monotypic genus *Kewthicata* and its sole species, *Kewthicata juliae*.

2.5 Skirts

The standalone gathered, straight, and parabola skirts are *incertae sedis* within the phylum Castula (Latin for "skirt").

The LCT-01’s terminology for the Kew skirts are somewhat counterintuitive; in the LCT-01 sense, the *straight* skirt refers to the skirt from the base Kew pattern (rightmost line art in Chang-Smith (2017a)), while the expansion pack explicitly names two skirts, a *gathered* and *straight* skirt. The line art for the aforementioned two skirts is on the left and right side of “Version 3” respectively in Chang-Smith (n.d.). The *straight* skirt from the expansion pack is referred to as the *parabola* skirt in the LCT-01, due to its shape.

Arguably, the base skirt from the original pattern could be considered parabolic in shape. The *straight* skirt itself from the expansion pack bulges slightly before it begins to curve inward at a shallow 181–185° angle.

Even if the terminology is inaccurate, it is now set in stone, both in the names of Kew genera and the standard-

ized terminology of LCT-01 descriptions. We will not be revising this terminology, but have described it for ease of reference.

We place the standalone Kew skirts in the family Kewcasaceae, divided into the genera *Kewplicasa* (gathered), *Kewparacasa* (parabola), and *Kewisicasa* (straight).

2.5.1 Kewbello

New to the taxonomy, and first introduced in this paper, in the sense that its documentation predates the first edits on Lemuria’s internal MediaWiki site, is the Kewbello, a jumpsuit created as a hybrid of the Kew dress and Portobello trousers.

We place the Portobello trousers in the family Portobelliidae, *incertae sedis* in the kingdom Suprapatella.

3 Methods

The author conducted his research on a computer running Ubuntu 24.04, with the XFCE desktop environment. He used the SHA2-256 algorithms to compute the cryptographic hashes of the photographic specimens he examined for species descriptions. He used Firefox 139.0.4. His monitor is a 55.8 cm (22 in) wide, 30.48 cm (12 in) tall, 63.5 cm (25 in) diagonal monitor, the NVISION S2515-B 25” IPS with a 100Hz refresh rate. He is not colorblind. He is near sighted and wears glasses.

The versions of the `sha256sum` and `openssl` utilities on his system at the time of the paper are given in the below terminal output:

```
$ sha256sum --version
sha256sum (GNU coreutils) 9.4
Copyright (C) 2023 Free Software Foundation, Inc.
License GPLv3+: GNU GPL version 3 or later <https://gnu.org/licenses/gpl.html>.
This is free software: you are free to change and redistribute it.
There is NO WARRANTY, to the extent permitted by law.
```

Written by Ulrich Drepper, Scott Miller, and David Madore.

```
$ openssl --version
OpenSSL 3.5.0 8 Apr 2025 (Library: OpenSSL 3.5.0 8 Apr 2025)
$ sha256sum /usr/bin/sha256sum /usr/bin/openssl
f293048f65668883ee919eb3f4b12926aaa13362de0eb6e3b5716b915b18b35 /usr/bin/sha256sum
724acbe911513d13f52bae0b8969b20336cd8618fc67898a6bf7847bf1a270ad /usr/bin/openssl
```

3.1 Filtot and YouTube

In taxonomizing *K. kristinae* (see Section 4.8.5), we used `yt-dlp`, a command-line tool, to download Lehrer’s videos. We include terminal output in the *K. kristinae* section for how each file was downloaded and processed, instead of here.

To locate other videos on Lehrer’s channel where she discussed her Kew dress, we used the service Filtot, which indexes captions both automatic and manual, across some, according to its self-reported figures, 1.35 billion videos and 78 million channels.

We used the query (`cue | kew | q`) NEAR\10 dress. YouTube’s automatic captioning system frequently mishears “Kew” as “Q”, “queue”, or “cue”, hence the parenthetical.

The URL for the query is as follows: [https://filmot.com/search/\(cue%20%7C%20kew%20%7C%20q\)%20NEAR%5C10%20dress/1?channelID=UCKOvDKc-vLr_pbvJL7KoLXg&gridView=1&](https://filmot.com/search/(cue%20%7C%20kew%20%7C%20q)%20NEAR%5C10%20dress/1?channelID=UCKOvDKc-vLr_pbvJL7KoLXg&gridView=1&)

3.2 holotyper tool

During work on this paper, we authored a small Golang command-line tool to read EXIF metadata from photos to automatically fill in certain details, such as focal length, f-stop, and exposure, to save time and allow us to focus on writing descriptions and examining the specimens.

The code is rudimentary and unpolished, but we hope to release it eventually to allow transparency and reproducibility.

4 Species descriptions

We also present additional species descriptions of the taxa we have covered.

First public description (first public desc.) indicates that this paper is the first public description of the species, and that the taxon was first documented privately on Lemuria’s MediaWiki site.

4.1 Genus *Florankewia*

Florankewia Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Diagnosis: Hybrid of three patterns. Bodice from the By Hand London (BHL) pattern Flora (Behelafloridae; unpublished), with sleeves of Kewoidea, and skirt of the By Hand London pattern Anna.

4.1.1 *Florankewia libera*

Florankewia libera Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Holotype: *Eva 4be-FL* Photograph. 1104×1104. EXIF metadata stripped; exposure, f-stop, lens foc. len unknown. United Kingdom, London. Ventral full-body view. Dorsally positioned hair, straps unobscured. *Florankewia libera* wb. Eva, 2019. © Kate Eva or unknown photographer, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Eva (2019a).
- **SHA2-256:** 2db411c534a464ef21bcb247128f3583a006954b7c16d7b3e188fe381eec1f0b
- **Raw image URLs**
 - **Original:** <https://kateevadesigns.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/05/f4f5d0b1-5a27-44d7-9055-77eba812a4be.jpg>
 - **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260316223517/https://kateevadesigns.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/05/f4f5d0b1-5a27-44d7-9055-77eba812a4be.jpg>

Description: Flat neckline. Sleeves typical to that of Kewoidea. Medial torso segment of neckline superior to sleeve segment of neckline. Straps extended by unspecified amount. Neckline lowered ventrally, and to an unknown degree dorsally. Skirt drapes, terminates inferior to knee. Bilateral ventral slits on both legs, originating superior to knee.

Fabric. Unspecified fabric within the Wildwood collection by Rifle Paper Co. Numerous unidentified flowers.

Etymology: *libera* is a pseudo-Latin feminine form of Liberty, the department store where Eva and Bond met.

Remarks: In Eva (2019a), Eva wrote that at the Liberty department store in London, she attended a signing event held by Anna Bond, the chief creative officer of Rifle Paper Co. She approached Bond wearing a Martha dress from Tilly and the Buttons (unclassified as of 2026-03-17), made in rayon from Rifle Paper Co. Bond and Eva then had a friendly interaction; and Bond later sent Eva rayon from the Wildwood collection, unreleased at the time, which arrived some months later. The name of the collection was inferred from imagery of the fabric itself showing the label “RIFLE PAPER CO Wildwood COLLECTION”.

Specimens examined: See holotype information.

4.1.2 *Florankewia valentina*

Florankewia valentina Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Holotype: *Eva 0098FV* — Photograph. 1440×1440. EXIF metadata stripped; exposure, f-stop, lens foc. len unknown. United Kingdom, London. Ventral full-body view. Dorsally positioned hair. *Florankewia valentina* wb. Eva, 2019. © Kate Eva or unknown photographer, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Eva (2019b).
- **SHA2-256:** 259d9687e6e09752364856a59620d7ffa15d28ded0e669b529a08f5e8bbc3332
- **Raw image URLs**
 - **Original:** <https://kateevadesigns.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/09/9a19be8e-4b8a-472f-9f03-1b917380098c.jpg>
 - **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260315224227/https://kateevadesigns.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/09/9a19be8e-4b8a-472f-9f03-1b917380098c.jpg>

Description: Flat neckline. Sleeves typical to that of *Kewoidea*. Medial torso segment of neckline superior to sleeve segment of neckline. Dorsal medial zipper, sky blue. Straps extended by unspecified number of inches. Neckline lowered ventrally, and to a greater degree dorsally. Skirt drapes, terminates inferior to knee. **Fabric.** Ex-designer fabric, from Fabric Godmother pop up at New Craft House. Purchased c. 2018 by Eva. Shell pattern with pale sky blue background and scallop-like print. Scallops have white background with black border and lines. **Lining.** Bluish pink gossamer crepe on bodice. Skirt fully unlined.

Etymology: Feminine form of *valentino*.

Specimens examined:

- Holotype.
- *Eva 3222FV*⁷ — Photograph. 1440×1440. EXIF metadata stripped; exposure, f-stop, lens foc. len unknown. United Kingdom, London. Dorsal half-body view.
 - **Page:** See Eva (2019b).
 - **SHA2-256:** c4b0476878da7f7011d353fed70da76235731be5edd1416c21203809c74291af
 - **Raw image URLs**
 - * **Original:** <https://kateevadesigns.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/09/c573e2db-5b6d-4658-8832-2b6145a9ec96.jpg>;
 - * **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260316080324/https://kateevadesigns.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/09/c573e2db-5b6d-4658-8832-2b6145a9ec96.jpg>;

4.2 Genus *Helikewabotonia*

Helikewabotonia gen. nov.

Diagnosis: Distinguished from *Kewabotonia* by the lack of sleeves lateral to the upper arm.

4.2.1 *Helikewabotonia lanata*

Helikewabotonia lanata sp. nov.

Holotype: *Joy 112.26042HL* — Photograph. 1080×1258. EXIF metadata stripped. Photographed 2018-05-06. Ventral view, hair positioned ventrally, obscuring straps. *Helikewabotonia lanata* wb. Joy of B., 2018; © Joy (@sew.with.joy), 2018, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Joy of B. (2018)
- **SHA2-256:** b71e212b9cc918658913cb8a88e5c7b314652211979a6e3f4d6f2e2203e01631
- **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260320151540/https://instagram.fmnl35-1.fna.fbcdn.net/v/t51.82787-15/649058460_18312888976269800_7157007690988526042_n.jpg?stp=dst-jpg_e35_tt6&_nc_cat=103&ig_cache_key=MTc3MzQ4Nzg2MzY3ODM3NTU0Mw%3D%3D.3-ccb7-5&ccb=7-5&_nc_sid=58cdad&efg=eyJ2ZW5jb2RlX3RhZyI6InhwaWRzLjEwODB4MTI1OC5zZHIuQzZMifQ%3D%3D&_nc_ohc=EBovqWWs06MQ7kNvwFSvfvr&_nc_oc=

⁷Derived from 0xc96 converted to decimal.

[AdoPp8j2FsMwCn8fYgS75vcxhWhVHhVNI3T9kd-7VVJbpbBknRF7bJORBj4duOb38ME&_nc_ad=z-m&_nc_cid=0&_nc_zt=23&_nc_ht=instagram.fmnl35-1.fna&_nc_gid=lLeRgI1OxmGROFj_coFwk&_nc_ss=7a30f&oh=00_Afzg-ZNO_vk3brOGiKIUg9BI4MeHPlxORu9QOj3t31f7lg&oe=69C33297](https://www.instagram.com/p/AdoPp8j2FsMwCn8fYgS75vcxhWhVHhVNI3T9kd-7VVJbpbBknRF7bJORBj4duOb38ME&_nc_ad=z-m&_nc_cid=0&_nc_zt=23&_nc_ht=instagram.fmnl35-1.fna&_nc_gid=lLeRgI1OxmGROFj_coFwk&_nc_ss=7a30f&oh=00_Afzg-ZNO_vk3brOGiKIUg9BI4MeHPlxORu9QOj3t31f7lg&oe=69C33297)

Description: Shallow angle V neck. Curved neckline medially. Lack of ventral medial button row. Bilateral single straps. **Fabric.** Unknown material. Extremely light cyan background, stylized watermelon slice pattern.

Etymology: Feminine form of *lanatus*, specific epithet of the watermelon (*Citrullus lanatus* (Thunb.) Matsum. & Nakai), from the fabric.

Remarks:

- Joy lives in Brooklyn. As a disambiguator prefix, Brooklyn’s post code, 112, is appended.
- In her Instagram post, Joy mentioned that she used the Gingerthread Girl’s hack.

Specimens examined:

- Holotype.
- **Joy 112.69087HL** — Photograph. 1080×1253. EXIF metadata stripped. Photographed 2018-05-06. Zoomed out ventral view, river in background, outdoors. Worn under unclassified white garment. *Helikewabotonia lanata* wb. Joy of B., 2018; © Joy (@sew.with.joy), 2018, all rights reserved.
 - **Page:** See Joy of B. (2018)
 - **SHA2-256:** e672017ce9a8243b070f65f804b27736faefa2fdb6b33396cd6469037cb3343e
 - **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260320151536/https://instagram.fmnl35-1.fna.fbcdn.net/v/t51.82787-15/653728557_18563423779053644_4275307087395769087_n.jpg?stp=dst-jpg_e35_tt6&_nc_cat=110&ig_cache_key=MTc3MzQ4Nzg1NTg2ODc2NzM5OA%3D%3D.3-ccb7-5&ccb=7-5&_nc_sid=58cdad&efg=eyJ2ZW5jb2RlX3RhZy16InhwaWRzLjEwODB4MTI1My5zZHIuQzMiMifQ%3D%3D&_nc_ohc=jAWlaQR5oPUQ7kNvwFYpiXT&_nc_oc=AdrOcmXdXPWI3FHjFyT1OMRUwmtq2819T8ASY3frqjXe4i2l9LSFY8TKLm61X8x2IgU&_nc_ad=z-m&_nc_cid=0&_nc_zt=23&_nc_ht=instagram.fmnl35-1.fna&_nc_gid=lLeRgI1OxmGROFj_coFwk&_nc_ss=7a30f&oh=00_Afw_vCjAysfjeK-Hi6zsUQRpi_pxKEEnQRXQOdQHx_01Lmg&oe=69C32662

4.2.2 *Helikewabotonia stadile*

Helikewabotonia stadile sp. nov.

Holotype: *Emma 2019-001.HS* — Photograph. 1102×2048. EXIF metadata stripped. *Helikewabotonia stadile* wb. Emma of N., 2019. © Emma of Crafty Clyde, 2019, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Emma of N. (2019)
- **SHA2-256:** db9b04c2fad0a27e80a5da3a32f0cade8420b281acb1fec4f3e8d7be38ae39cb
- **Raw image URLs**
 - **Original:** https://blogger.googleusercontent.com/img/b/R29vZ2xl/AVvXsEjgWW0S9_NZtjgvjQW7vIAuJP0D5T0WcWoC86-LKxsiHtzShlKg5RfpbLMxvovfHudGigTls3Qgz_7ynh3cf4ouH0340qbHHVw9jI-GjsZyJxof5sk77qXgw7oO6OQOlVd0mzQ7ybiWV_Q/s0/holland.JPG=s0?imgmax=0
 - **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260319090301/https://blogger.googleusercontent.com/img/b/R29vZ2xl/AVvXsEjgWW0S9_NZtjgvjQW7vIAuJP0D5T0WcWoC86-LKxsiHtzShlKg5RfpbLMxvovfHudGigTls3Qgz_7ynh3cf4ouH0340qbHHVw9jI-GjsZyJxof5sk77qXgw7oO6OQOlVd0mzQ7ybiWV_Q/s0/holland.JPG=s0?imgmax=0

Description: Shallow angle V-neck. Lack of ventral medial button row. Bilateral single straps. Bilateral pockets on skirt. Size 14. Skirt terminates superior to knee. **Fabric.** “Dutch Farm” print from Timeless Treasures. Bodice depicts front of red barn, doors open. Skirt features field of tulips (*Tulipa* L.). Pattern discontinuity at bodice–skirt seam.

Etymology: From Medieval Latin *stadile* “barn”.

Specimens examined: See holotype information.

4.3 Genus *Helikewisia*

Helikewisia Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Diagnosis: Distinguished from genera in Kewoidea by the lack of sleeves lateral to upper arm, and a skirt most similar to *Kewisicasa* (straight skirt).

4.3.1 *Helikewisia aemilia*

Helikewisia aemilia Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Holotype: *Emily 3668HA* — Photograph. 1184×1480. Exposure: 1/80s. F-stop: 2. Focal: 23 mm. Lens: unknown. Camera: Fujifilm X100T. Ventral view. *Helikewisia aemilia* wb. Emily of L., 2017. © Emily or unknown photographer, 2017, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Emily of L. (2017)
- **SHA2-256:** 91098a2dd37df4410add3dd1b148aaebb1ddda1f0e6958ff736f83b59d5f7191
- **Raw image URLs**
 - **Original:** https://selfassemblyrequired.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/2017/09/img_3668.jpg
 - **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260317182014/https://selfassemblyrequired.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/2017/09/img_3668.jpg

Description: Shallow V-neck. Ventral medial button row. UK size 10. Bilateral single straps. Straps pattern-match with bodice; dark blue transition bilaterally superior to dorsal attachment point. Skirt terminates inferior to knee. **Fabric.** Striped poly crepe, vertical lines. From wearer's left to right, dark blue, pink, sky blue, cyan, orange, white, dark blue, orange, red, white, cyan, purple, sky blue, dark blue, white, red, orange, dark blue. Color bands horizontal on straps. **Buttons.** Unknown black reflective material, circular inset. Unknown color of thread, unknown number of thread holes on button.

Etymology: *Aemilia*, Latin form of *Emily*.

Remarks:

- In *Emily 3668HA*, the dress drapes and obscures the inferior part of the ventral medial button row.

Specimens examined:

- Holotype.
- *Emily 3670HA* — Photograph. 1184×1480. Exposure: 1/80s. F-stop: 2. Focal: 23 mm. Lens: unknown. Camera: Fujifilm X100T. Dorsal view. *Helikewisia aemilia* wb. Emily, 2017. © Emily or unknown photographer, 2017, all rights reserved.
 - **Page:** See Emily of L. (2017)
 - **SHA2-256:** ec3e3d936e67833f60199384f2f824afe2bf8d3ac771e1a526800815659f2575
 - **Raw image URLs**
 - * **Original:** https://selfassemblyrequired.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/2017/09/img_3670.jpg
 - * **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260317182001/https://selfassemblyrequired.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/2017/09/img_3670.jpg

4.3.2 *Helikewisia ceciliae*

Helikewisia ceciliae Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Holotype: *Cecilia 849728HC* — Photograph. 1080×1080. EXIF metadata stripped; exposure, f-stop, lens foc. len unknown. United Kingdom, London, Kew, Kew Gardens. Angled ventral view, roughly 45° horizontal, 45° vertical, subject on stairs. *Helikewisia ceciliae* wb. Cecilia C., 2018. © Cecilia Cook or unknown photographer, 2017, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Cecilia C. (2018)
- **SHA2-256:** 4ba6fc17376db5e455e5f8a76917a9e98d1c7e1602083f3b17da957dc1b04076
- **Raw image URLs**
 - **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318084447/https://scontent.fmnl35-1.fna.fbcdn.net/v/t1.6435-9/38796551_2234719783416504_779248449227849728_n.jpg?_nc_ohc=OfvYHoRETDIQ7kNvwGegeMe&_nc_oc=AdkuqDYsozC3fEwo02nMcm-dwyBiAQmRw-KsWR-1xgDLFo1nRiLEyILr78MbWb6UOJQ&_nc_zt=23&

nc_ht=scontent.fmnl35-1.fna&_nc_gid=nqbWH-IXJHbF6PSN-NvPOg&_nc_ss=8&oh=00_AfwMIGiSC8FvYlP D4FjhqdZm52v_78oVvwDlvPKQf6WK9w&oe=69E1D8BB

Description: Shallow angle V-neck. Bilateral single straps. Straps 2 in (5.08 cm) longer. Ventral medial button row. Buttons fabric-covered, ~12 buttons visible; some buttons in holotype image obscured by skirt. Skirt termination point unknown due to angle of holotype image. **Fabric.** Jennifer crepe from Sew Me Sunshine, sunshine yellow background. Monochrome black and white floral line art print. Flower most closely resembles *Chrysanthemum × morifolium* (Ramat.) Hemsl.

Etymology: *Cecilia* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

Remarks:

- The Internet Archive is capable of capturing Meta CDN links. Though they lack long-term reproducibility, the Internet Archive can retrieve the same bytes, effectively “freezing” the image in time. We are thus able to maintain reproducibility for the Meta CDN, but here, we advise that the Internet Archive URL should be considered the canonical URL; the Meta CDN url is not expected to be reproducible long-term. It is embedded in the Internet Archive URL, and need not be printed separately to save space.

Specimens examined: See holotype information.

4.3.3 *Helikewisia erinae*

Helikewisia erinae Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Holotype: *Madalone 4823HE* — Photograph. 427×640, EXIF metadata stripped; exposure, f-stop, lens foc. len unknown. United States, New Jersey, Monmouth County, Holland Ridge Farms. Approx. GPS: 40.16936°N 74.50087°W ± 50m (WGS84). Instagram. Ventral view. Hair positioned ventrally, partially obscuring view of left strap (wearer’s perspective). *Helikewisia erinae* wb. Erin.M., 2021. Instagram. © Erin Madalone or unknown photographer, 2021, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Madalone (2021a) and Madalone (2021b)
- **SHA2-256:** ff6af1347c0f4ae0d17d74efce69ded5702681b0ea356233daa18e4c690f9a29.
- **Raw image URLs**
 - **Original:** <https://mypoeticmemory.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/9f49e8f1-0424-4b0a-ada4-5829431c4823.jpeg>
 - **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260316212935/https://mypoeticmemory.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/9f49e8f1-0424-4b0a-ada4-5829431c4823.jpeg>

Description: Shallow angle V-neck. Bilateral single straps. **Fabric.** Rayon. “Strawberry Fields Rayon in Ivory”, Rifle Paper Co. Wildflowers. Numerous flowers, including but not limited to, *Centaurea cyanus* L.; *Ranunculus repens* L. **Buttons.** Emerald-green like. Unknown reflective material, likely plastic. White thread, two thread holes. Buttons attached to left side of bodice (wearer’s perspective).

Etymology: *Erin* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

Remarks:

- *Madalone Inst-1HE* specimen was obtained using instaloader. Direct right-click from original Instagram page returns slightly higher-resolution image. Meta’s CDN infrastructure is in general, unreceptive to reproducible image retrievals due to the large amount of parameters involved. URLs also appear to have expiring signatures.
- Holotype specimen is of significantly lower quality, but it is reproducible. A debate is due as to whether image quality or image reproducibility should be valued more in selecting a holotype.
- The degree to which floral patterns should be documented; and whether the LCT-01 should create a new domain dedicated to fabric taxonomy, is a subject of future discussion. Most of the flowers are likely stylized, and if they correspond to valid botanical names, cannot be conclusively identified due to the author’s lack of experience in botany.

Specimens examined:

- Holotype.

- **Madalone Inst-1HE** — Photograph. 1080×1350, EXIF metadata stripped; exposure, f-stop, lens foc. len unknown. United States, New Jersey, Monmouth County, Holland Ridge Farms. Approx. GPS: 40.16936°N 74.50087°W ± 50m (WGS84). Instagram. Ventral view. Hair positioned ventrally, partially obscuring view of left strap (wearer’s perspective). *Helikewisia erinae* wb. Erin.M., 2021. Higher-resolution version of holotype, but unreproducible due to Meta CDN implementation details. Unshareable due to copyright. © Erin Madalone or unknown photographer, 2021, all rights reserved.
 - **SHA2-256:** 062cd32b6a0eb3b2c8803055384cc473db1fd5959d5616b5229bacb6488baac8.

4.3.4 *Helikewisia irvinae*

Helikewisia irvinae Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Holotype: *Irvine 0001HI* — Photograph. 2736×3648. Exposure 1/665 sec, f-stop 1.6, lens foc. len 5.6mm (35mm equiv. 27.0mm), ISO 50, FOV 67.4°, no flash. United Kingdom. Ventral full-body view. Tied hair. Hands in bilateral pockets. *Helikewisia irvinae* wb. Alice.Ir., 2020. © Alice Irvine or unknown photographer, 2020, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Irvine (2020a).
- **SHA2-256:** 56018b2b4de1d041abe40308ea36c514cbc2a433348038445e94c1a17ae3a34d
- **Raw image URLs**
 - **Original:** <https://aliceirvine.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/nina-lee-kew-dress-1.jpg>
 - **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260316225915/https://aliceirvine.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/nina-lee-kew-dress-1.jpg>

Description: Bilateral single straps with medial tie. Straight skirt with lateral gathering. Ventral medial button row of nine buttons; three on bodice, six on skirt. Skirt terminates inferior to knee. Diamond-shaped buttons, orange. Button thread holes and thread line at 45° angle to edges. Ventral lateral darts lowered by 2 cm. Subaxillary seam lowered by 1 cm. Bodice lengthened by 4 cm. Side seams sewed at 1 cm allowance for slightly relaxed fit. Bilateral ventral pockets run from parallel to fifth button and terminate slightly superior to seventh button’s parallel. Four pleats on pocket. Bodice lined.

Etymology: *Irvine* + *-ae*, feminine genitive form.

Remarks: Irvine wrote in Irvine (2020a) that after washing *H. irvinae*, the shorter seam allowance softened. Prior to this, it had sat “strangely” on the bust. The buttons were repurposed from a Tilly and the Buttons Arielle skirt Irvine made earlier⁸. Irvine wrote a tutorial for the pockets in Irvine (2020b).

Specimens examined: See holotype information.

4.3.5 *Helikewisia kristinae*

Helikewisia kristinae sp. nov.

Holotype: *Lehrer 2018.88823HKEW* — Photograph. 1080×1350. EXIF metadata stripped by Meta CDN. Truncated ventral view, subject facing slightly downward. *Helikewisia kristinae* wb. Lehrer, 2018. © Kristin Lehrer, 2018, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Lehrer (2018b).
- **SHA2-256:** 7cd9db2581b2d8e914edd7fb3d04d2fa54ff4b0d09f644cb7bf96d7efd66334b
- **Raw image URLs**
 - **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260319132037/https://instagram.fmnl35-1.fna.fbcdn.net/v/t51.82787-15/651304872_18342211174243233_2394920789214788823_n.jpg?stp=dst-jpg_e35_tt6&_nc_ohc=FwrXTiN1G5wQ7kNvWfy_jZE&_nc_oc=AdpK-2DaeK0qlOT9rNzxyo0CRbOSvu3b-5B_Nz1RWHSRQzAizagKjJ8v1JxkgG1ziIE&_nc_ad=z-m&_nc_cid=0&_nc_zt=23&_nc_ht=instagram.fmnl35-1.fna&_nc_gid=K4_6pwiUZqSjFpoiU745AQ&_nc_ss=8&oh=00_AfweZfEjv2dAnJkONXV1jObK6mrzxkeRGxQhN5JYjG_sHQ&oe=69C1D13A

Description: Shallow angle V-neck. Bilateral single straps. Skirt terminates superior to knee. **Buttons.** Ventral medial button row, 13 buttons. Five on bodice, eight on skirt. Circular, two thread holes, black thread. Thread line mostly

⁸*incertae sedis* in the family Ariellacasaceae Lemuria, 2026

horizontal. **Fabric.** Black background. Repeating pattern of cat (*Felis catus*)-like facial expression. Two whiskers, two eyes. Cat pattern in white.

Etymology: *Kristin* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

Specimens examined:

- Holotype.
- **Lehrer 2018.43603HKEW** — Photograph. 1080×1345. EXIF metadata stripped by Meta CDN. Truncated ventral view, first three buttons visible. *Helikewisia kristinae* wb. Lehrer, 2018. © Kristin Lehrer, 2018, all rights reserved.
 - **Page:** See Lehrer (2018b).
 - **SHA2-256:** 7b1625cfe7649681197ae5840382c3596e66f74910362e54f9c18eeca56475e5
 - **Raw image URLs**
 - * **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260319132504/https://instagram.fmnl35-1.fna.fbcdn.net/v/t51.82787-15/653489959_18391307863150239_6596263911806943603_n.jpg?stp=dst-jpg_e35_tt6&_nc_cat=106&ig_cache_key=MTc4NjUyMjU4ODE5NDAwODUzOQ%3D%3D.3-ccb7-5&ccb=7-5&_nc_sid=58cdad&efg=eyJ2ZW5jb2RlX3RhZyI6InhwaWRzLjEwODB4MTM0NS5zZHIuQzMifQ%3D%3D&_nc_ohc=g0bLlB5Xx7MQ7kNvWFDxEeV&_nc_oc=AdqOJQDOWeGNSK4gMIIdnmZKuMUIRSQdhuEQ6h3ClRrQtmgJNmpx3nYc-0A2jPpPYkCE&_nc_ad=z-m&_nc_cid=0&_nc_zt=23&_nc_ht=instagram.fmnl35-1.fna&_nc_gid=cTsd1WJdPGRH6GhiGPqNBg&_nc_ss=8&oh=00_Afx1XhjsuVToExkKX3X08_ruhQ9gBxwOeUCTkdi1TdGDZg&oe=69C1D9D8
- **Lehrer 2018.22063HKEW** — Photograph. 1080×1350. EXIF metadata stripped by Meta CDN. *Helikewisia kristinae* wb. Lehrer, 2018. Full-body angled dorsal view, subject facing camera. © Kristin Lehrer, 2018, all rights reserved.
 - **Page:** See Lehrer (2018b).
 - **SHA2-256:** e34d04a4f4577ff12a97e703981e379fd4d86d5f2c161b61279c34b17f55c33c
 - **Raw image URLs:**
 - * **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260319132312/https://instagram.fmnl35-1.fna.fbcdn.net/v/t51.82787-15/649224321_18310689463248562_3345583525819022063_n.jpg?stp=dst-jpg_e35_tt6&_nc_ohc=wmaMrt1JT08Q7kNvWWh_cwn&_nc_oc=Adqm16almXh5DWJO1q2Ys7bNZbWdpHNzLws3N8gYbkUJ9n6SD4CJZ1tj-R0wBThvBu8&_nc_ad=z-m&_nc_cid=0&_nc_zt=23&_nc_ht=instagram.fmnl35-1.fna&_nc_gid=cTsd1WJdPGRH6GhiGPqNBg&_nc_ss=8&oh=00_Afz1hUBh7L5Olq8hXFOWMDV7aA0ETNm2ihpyAuru7huOfg&oe=69C1DF5A
- **Lehrer 2018.86738HKEW** — Photograph. 1080×1350. EXIF metadata stripped by Meta CDN. *Helikewisia kristinae* wb. Lehrer, 2018. © Kristin Lehrer, 2018, all rights reserved.
 - **Page:** See Lehrer (2018b).
 - **SHA2-256:** 814fa9cfad20ad414a965623eae02d11b82ecaa54b0522f0537d9ec7f762dac3
 - **Raw image URLs:**
 - * **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260319154054/https://instagram.fmnl35-1.fna.fbcdn.net/v/t51.82787-15/652736560_18566358889030125_2343636094538386738_n.jpg?stp=dst-jpg_e35_tt6&_nc_cat=104&ig_cache_key=MTc4NjUyMjU3NDc0Njk0MDk3NQ%3D%3D.3-ccb7-5&ccb=7-5&_nc_sid=58cdad&efg=eyJ2ZW5jb2RlX3RhZyI6InhwaWRzLjEwODB4MTM1MC5zZHIuQzMifQ%3D%3D&_nc_ohc=Ew8gBj5VlYgQ7kNvWgttAYi&_nc_oc=Adpd5jT5MgxYi8_Xuhv40GkC3THp8hpp-hiyebzQ4gVXsxD18DenMlAJiahBqE8pHk&_nc_ad=z-m&_nc_cid=0&_nc_zt=23&_nc_ht=instagram.fmnl35-1.fna&_nc_gid=4TKyJZiquFSWjl8edc6GHg&_nc_ss=8&oh=00_AfwJqGglsITxvVm6q7wykt5hwaPefNMpeL01lfeI6AGUw&oe=69C2079B
- **Lehrer 2018.94528HKEW** — Photograph. 1080×1350. EXIF metadata stripped by Meta CDN. *Helikewisia kristinae* wb. Lehrer, 2018. © Kristin Lehrer, 2018, all rights reserved.
 - **Page:** See Lehrer (2018b).
 - **SHA2-256:** e49d36f1d0da97a674453c3073e3437dab5835e8f4be30b1e2ba0a5808e38fee
 - **Raw image URLs:**
 - * **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260319154052/https://instagram.fmnl35-1.fna.fbcdn.net/v/t51.2885-15/32203412_2115508038733054_3655784219990294528_n.jpg?stp=dst-jpg_e35_tt6&_nc_cat=103&ig_cache_key=MTc4NjUyMjU5NjAxMjA3MjI3OAA%3D%3D.3-ccb7-5&ccb=7-5&_nc_sid=58cdad&efg=eyJ2ZW5jb2RlX3RhZyI6InhwaWRzLjEwODB4MTM1MC5zZHIuZGVmYXVsdF9pbWFnZS5DMjYj9&_nc_ohc=dRqDySO0u6wQ7kNvWGU3ovf&_nc_oc=AdpJH8WTAbySRnddi8ij7ZEK1SK1zXI-bvBznB10-

NjGnQ9LIqTxxoa0MFQsob6pS4&_nc_ad=z-m&_nc_cid=0&_nc_zt=23&_nc_ht=instagram.fmnl35-1.fna&_nc_ss=8&oh=00_AfxJnBJAutMp2fVzH8EAgnz_7LFzuzCHFbMpNxCX43ICGA&oe=69C1D48D

4.3.6 *Helikewisia mariae*

Helikewisia mariae sp. nov.

Holotype: *Maria 0001HM* — Photograph. 1454×2560. EXIF metadata stripped. *Helikewisia mariae* wb. Maria (pattern tester; W/2026 F1⁹), c. 2023. © Maria or unknown photographer

- **Page:** See Chang-Smith (2026)
- **SHA2-256:** ba74c7feec707a9bb6c815f761ebc1916697dfa1ab06c1be353133cc896a2f77
- **Raw image URLs:**
 - **Original:** <https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/products/Maria-Nina-Lee-Kew-Dress-Expansion-16-28-scaled.jpg?v=1677871708>
 - **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260320193417/https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/products/Maria-Nina-Lee-Kew-Dress-Expansion-16-28-scaled.jpg?v=1677871708>

Description: Shallow angle V-neck. Bilateral single straps. **Buttons.** Ventral medial button row of 23 buttons. Wood-like color. Four thread holes. **Fabric.** Unknown material. Plain pink fabric.

Etymology: *Maria* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

Specimens examined: See holotype information.

Remarks:

- Date inferred from Shopify CDN v parameter.

4.3.7 *Helikewisia sarae*

Helikewisia sarae sp. nov. **Holotype:** *Sarah 0082HS.AU-TAS* — Photograph. 902×1280. Exposure: 1/60s. F-stop: 3.3. Focal: 4.30 mm. ISO: 100. Camera: DMC-TZ40. Lens: unknown. *Helikewisia sarae* wb. Sarah of T., 2019. Ventral view, subject looking to right. © Sarah of *Craftily Handmade*, 2019, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Sarah of T. (2019)
- **SHA2-256:** 122bc658b0851718566a03e7a74bbb8c1b14f4464c65fe928ee9f5ab9de81690
- **Raw image URLs**
 - **Original:** <https://craftilyhandmade.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/02/p1040085.jpg>

Description: Shallow angle V neck, bilateral single straps. Buttonholes made of white thread. **Buttons.** Ventral medial button row, 12 buttons. Two thread holes, thread line vertical, **Fabric.** Floral rayon. White background. No known correspondence of artistic depictions to botanical taxa.

Etymology: *Sarah* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

Remarks:

- The *Craftily Handmade* blog returns HTML previews of images, which has impeded archival in the Internet Archive's Wayback Machine.
- We recommend verifying using the WARC files listed at <https://archive.fart.website/archivebot/viewer/domain/craftilyhandmade.wordpress.com>.
 - We were able to reproduce the SHA2-256 signatures using the WARC files in https://archive.org/download/archiveteam_archivebot_go_20260319211301_2cc8aa60.

Specimens examined:

- Holotype.
- *Sarah 0085HS.AU-TAS* — Photograph. 960×1280. Exposure: 1/60s. F-stop: 3.3. Focal: 4.30 mm. ISO: 100. Camera: DMC-TZ40. Lens: unknown. *Helikewisia sarae* wb. Sarah of T., 2019. Angled ventral view, subject looking down. © Sarah of *Craftily Handmade*, 2019, all rights reserved.

⁹An “Unnamable Human(oid) Center” identifier, assigned for disambiguation purposes.

- **Page:** See Sarah of T. (2019)
- **SHA2-256:** b5aeadf6a255e68882965fbb93f03231974fb02e199a6da3277f2c77cbdee42
- **Raw image URLs**
 - * **Original:** <https://craftilyhandmade.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/02/p1040085.jpg>
- **Sarah 0087HS.AU-TAS** — Photograph. 960×1280. Exposure: 1/60s. F-stop: 3.3. Focal: 4.30 mm. ISO: 100. Camera: DMC-TZ40. Lens: unknown. Dorsal view, hair positioned ventrally. *Helikewisia sarae* wb. Sarah of T., 2019. © Sarah of *Craftily Handmade*, 2019, all rights reserved.
 - **Page:** See Sarah of T. (2019)
 - **SHA2-256:** 0870318792544de291a1d5b8b74f8efb1c9e11bf5af062db37d19650f6822bec
 - **Raw image URLs**
 - * **Original:** <https://craftilyhandmade.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/02/p1040087.jpg>
- **Sarah 0088HS.AU-TAS** — Photograph. 960×1280. Exposure: 1/80s. F-stop: 5.6. Focal: 38.20 mm. ISO: unknown. Camera: DMC-TZ40. Lens: unknown. Close ventral view of button row. © Sarah of *Craftily Handmade*, 2019, all rights reserved.
 - **Page:** See Sarah of T. (2019)
 - **SHA2-256:** c6915eed7b3a04d442317a160b5c39f97bb71efd05427380c9db416a3d674aa4
 - **Raw image URLs**
 - * **Original:** <https://craftilyhandmade.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/03/p1040088.jpg>

4.4 Genus *Helikewisia* subg. *Emmae*

In August 2019, Emma, the author of the blog *Crafty Clyde*, sewed three Kew dresses; two of which have a ventral medial button row. We place the new species *H. arbor* and *H. quagga* into the subgenus *Emmae*.

Diagnosis: Having been sewn by Emma of N.

4.4.1 *Helikewisia arbor*

Helikewisia arbor sp. nov.

Holotype: *Emma 2019-001.HA* — Photograph. 1819×2048. EXIF metadata stripped. *Helikewisia arbor* wb. Emma of N., 2019. © Emma of *Crafty Clyde*, 2019, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Emma of N. (2019)
- **SHA2-256:** 1cc632efa01d6e9461407572896ed51146b1c3e28e6375ba1231aa3f66742981
- **Raw image URLs**
 - **Original:** https://blogger.googleusercontent.com/img/b/R29vZ2xl/AVvXsEinnVliBaxEn9dtuWlB4GfXT-IO_aw_XzTxP0CE_fs_BuvuZ-ZqyFUUzCN01ub2TsumDbvTAXQI-V8T13sngx2M4BSUEuLCitYk2L5QwSKSw87jt4rA9JIqtHMBgpozynAsuxzv4RxhhCpw/s0/kew+green+2.JPG=s0?imgmax=0
 - **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260319091343/https://blogger.googleusercontent.com/img/b/R29vZ2xl/AVvXsEinnVliBaxEn9dtuWlB4GfXT-IO_aw_XzTxP0CE_fs_BuvuZ-ZqyFUUzCN01ub2TsumDbvTAXQI-V8T13sngx2M4BSUEuLCitYk2L5QwSKSw87jt4rA9JIqtHMBgpozynAsuxzv4RxhhCpw/s0/kew+green+2.JPG=s0?imgmax=0

Description: Shallow angle V neck. Bilateral pockets. **Buttons.** Ventral medial button row, approx. 12 buttons. Four on bodice, eight on skirt. Buttonholes have white thread. Buttons are pink, four thread holes. White/off-white thread cross each other. **Fabric.** “Divine Landscapes” viscose from Sewisfaction. Primary colors teal and green, repeating tree print. No known correlation to botanical taxa.

Etymology: From Latin *arbor* “tree”.

Specimens examined: See holotype information.

4.4.2 *Helikewisia quagga*

Helikewisia quagga sp. nov.

Holotype: *Emma K01.HQ* — Photograph. 1067×2048. EXIF metadata stripped. Ventral view. Dress on mannequin. © Emma of *Crafty Clyde*, 2019, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Emma of N. (2019)
- **SHA2-256:** 81faf393fa07bc693730e7a261e4286fb5a9fa406babb6be6bd883fc8e0bd9c9
- **Raw image URLs**
 - **Original:** https://blogger.googleusercontent.com/img/b/R29vZ2xl/AVvXsEiIozsKf9TE4sQKFm3DkT4aSsYMRCZEmLvsoYW0c-oCjuIKia4ZrRgBoWaCizBJLCEyFkS6G8S-4BR7Y4Nec7DUWdZT7wQzRp9I1UGIUK3jQmICcH2-N58lNMQVDDe7tzhylr75_Ogc/s0/zebra+kew.JPG=s0?imgmax=0
 - **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318235744/https://blogger.googleusercontent.com/img/b/R29vZ2xl/AVvXsEiIozsKf9TE4sQKFm3DkT4aSsYMRCZEmLvsoYW0c-oCjuIKia4ZrRgBoWaCizBJLCEyFkS6G8S-4BR7Y4Nec7DUWdZT7wQzRp9I1UGIUK3jQmICcH2-N58lNMQVDDe7tzhylr75_Ogc/s0/zebra+kew.JPG=s0?imgmax=0

Description: Shallow angle V neck. Bilateral pockets. **Buttons.** Ventral medial button row, approx. 11–12 buttons. Three on bodice, one roughly parallel to bodice–skirt transition line. 7–8 on skirt. Dark orange. Four thread holes, circular inset. Thread hole alignment variable. **Fabric.** Cotton fabric from Fabrics Galore. Yellow background. Zebra print (*Equus quagga* Boddaert, 1785).

Etymology: From the specific name of *Equus quagga* Boddaert, 1785, due to the zebra print.

Remarks:

- The inferiormost button is unfastened in *Emma K01.HQ*, and the fabric drape conceals it, if it exists. Thus, its existence cannot be proven.
- *Emma K01.HQ* only shows the dress on a mannequin; there is no human body for reference, so the length of the skirt cannot be determined.
- Emma sewed the dress for her sister.

Specimens examined: See holotype information.

4.5 Genus *Helikewplicata*

Helikewplicata gen. nov.

Diagnosis: Distinguished from other genera in tribe Helikewini by the presence of gathering on the superior area of the skirt, immediately inferior to the bodice–skirt transition.

4.5.1 *Helikewplicata ninae*

Helikewplicata ninae sp. nov.

Holotype: *Nina 0001HN* — Photograph. 2538×3508. EXIF metadata stripped. Zoomed-out slightly angled ventral shot. Subject facing downward. Hair positioned ventrally, obscuring wearer’s left strap. Subject in shade of tree, unknown species. *Helikewplicata ninae* wb. Nina, 2018. © Nina Chang-Smith, 2018, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Chang-Smith (2018)
- **SHA2-256:** 0a345c3809d7807cc00060e18700868e18035eaa4d5122836aa8e67ce18617ae
- **Raw image URLs**
 - **Original:** <https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0725/7833/5029/files/Gathered-Kew-Box-Hill.jpg>
 - **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260321204121im_/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0725/7833/5029/files/Gathered-Kew-Box-Hill.jpg

Description: Shallow angle V-neck. Bilateral single straps. **Buttons.** Ventral medial button row. 15 buttons. Five on bodice, ten on skirt. Unknown reflective material. Eighth button reflects light; possibly two thread holes. **Skirt.** Skirt terminates inferior to knee. Two vertical regions; first region runs from end of bodice to roughly 2.5 button lengths inferior to final button, with vertical stripes, before transition to rotated fabric pattern with horizontal stripes, sometimes slightly angled downward. **Fabric.** Unknown material. White–light blue stripes; ~4–5 bars in same space as width of 1 button.

Etymology: *Nina* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

Specimens examined: See holotype information.

4.6 Genus *Kewabotonia*

Kewabotonia Lemuria, 2026

Diagnosis: Phenetically, lack of ventral medial button row on both bodice and skirt. Phylogenetically, descent from Jen Walker's Kew hack (*Kewabotonia zingibera*, see Section 4.6.5).

4.6.1 *Kewabotonia eleanorae*

Kewabotonia eleanorae Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Holotype: *Eleanor* 2018.64378KE — Photograph. 1080×1350. EXIF metadata stripped. Ventral view of subject, leaning to her left. *Kewabotonia eleanorae* wb. Eleanor S. (W/2026 F3), 2018. © Eleanor (@eleanor_sews), 2018, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Chang-Smith (2018) and Eleanor Sews (2018)
- **SHA2-256:** ef9c601074e50d251fd783834625e3b557eea2c25469ab806d6c8770a2b60c81
- **Raw image URLs**
 - **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260322160151/https://instagram.fmnl35-1.fna.fbcdn.net/v/t51.82787-15/628177705_18425150422142088_1243896957829664378_n.jpg?stp=dst-jpg_e35_tt6&_nc_cat=107&ig_cache_key=MTgzNjQ4MDI3NDgwMDg4OTc4Ng%3D%3D.3-ccb7-5&ccb=7-5&_nc_sid=58cdad&efg=eyJ2ZW5jb2RlX3RhZy16InhwaWRZLjEwODB4MTM1MC5zZHIuQzMiMifQ%3D%3D&_nc_ohc=AYZw5nr_JeAQ7kNvwEVrRVA&_nc_oc=AdpsMC6QhwWqg7H4F46bfnyuTqX5XDwKSmbcpzT2fvDBtElq72qKaiD-4_poWLEmPOA&_nc_ad=z-m&_nc_cid=0&_nc_zt=23&_nc_ht=instagram.fmnl35-1.fna&_nc_gid=313aaxPBB4Xxq6LhKBlOlQ&_nc_ss=7a32e&oh=00_Afys_Sq3qMq-DOFfNLGPQz-FJ6oLX_-V01hgwp_mJETibw&oe=69C5E251

Description: Shallow angle V-neck. Curved neckline medially. Bilateral single straps. Lack of ventral medial button row. **Skirt.** Skirt terminates superior to knee. **Fabric.** Unknown poly cotton. Cyan background. Floral; stylized depiction of flamingo (*Phoenicoptera* Bonaparte, 1831) standing on *Hibiscus × rosa-sinensis* L.

Etymology: *Eleanor* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

Specimens examined: See holotype information.

4.6.2 *Kewabotonia elsa*

Kewabotonia elsa Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Holotype: *Elsa* 2021.0013KE — Photograph. 640×1080. Exposure: 1/50s. F-stop: 2.0. Focal: 3.51 mm. ISO: unknown. Lens: unknown. Camera: Redmi Note 7. *Kewabotonia elsa* wb. Elsa of L., 2021. © Elsa of *La Casa Cactus*, 2021, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Elsa of L. (2021)
- **SHA2-256:** 801293dddc4076f143b5c2a1eb2a539480a32ea4c7066ecbeb4a8c6932bcfccec
- **Raw image URLs**
 - **Original:** https://lacasacactus.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/kew_13.jpg
 - **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260319105749/https://lacasacactus.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/kew_13.jpg

Description: Shallow angle V neck. Lack of ventral medial button row. Bilateral single straps. Dorsal medial zipper. Skirt terminates superior to knee. **Fabric.** Brocade. Medium-weight, unknown brand, unknown name, purple background, purple decorations. Solid light purple/magenta lining.

Etymology: *Elsa* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

Specimens examined: See holotype information.

4.6.3 *Kewabotonia nuptirachaelae*

Kewabotonia nuptirachaelae Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Holotype: *Rachael 0063*¹⁰ — Photograph. 3600×2400. Exposure: 1/125s. F-stop: 8. Focal: 41 mm. Camera: Canon EOS 5D Mark IV. Lens: EF24–105mm f/4L IS II USM. *Kewabotonia nuptirachaelae* and 4 other *incertae sedis* species on hangers. © Chris Chambers, 2018, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Beaumont (2018a)
- **SHA2-256:** e2bd19110cb129884424e0a9cb40356b6d8f4913ccf2c50b9742b6de638e498e
- **Raw image URLs**
 - **Original:** <https://sewprettyful.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/08/0063-ra.jpg>

Description: Bilateral single straps. Lack of ventral medial button row. Full circle skirt. Interior white lining, with purple ink “Hand Crafted by Sewprettyful” label positioned medially on interior dorsal lining. Full overlay on bodice and skirt, plain band at bodice–skirt transition on transpyloric plane. White layers of fabric deep to outer layer.
Fabric.

Etymology: Latin *nuptiae* “marriage” + *Rachael* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

Remarks:

- Rachael sewed five dresses for her wedding’s bridesmaids. The maid of honor amongst the five, Lizzy, desired a cold-shoulder look, and Rachael accordingly used the Kew pattern, after modifying it to remove the ventral medial button row.
- We could not determine if there was any phylogenetic descent from Walker’s hack, which we are confident exists in the other four spp. of *Kewabotonia*.
- The other four dresses that Rachael sewed for her bridesmaids warrant their own taxonomic treatment.
- Only *Kewabotonia nuptirachaelae* had an overlay on its skirt; Rachael’s other four bridesmaids had plain full-circle skirts instead.
- While submitting <https://web.archive.org/web/20260317150922/https://sewprettyful.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/08/0063-ra.jpg> to the Internet Archive, Save Page Now failed to capture the JPG image properly due to improper content negotiation. WordPress instead returned an HTML preview of the image.
- As such, we recommend these links for verifying the archive:
 - https://archive.org/details/archiveteam_archivebot_go_20260320094602_3d45c6e0
 - Other Archiveteam archives for Rachael’s blog may be indexed at <https://archive.fart.website/archivebot/viewer/domain/sewprettyful.wordpress.com>.

Specimens examined:

- Holotype.
- *Rachael 0412* — Photograph. 3600×2400. Exposure: 1/1250s. F-stop: 4.5. Focal: 70 mm. Camera: Canon EOS 5D Mark IV. Lens: EF70–200mm f/2.8L IS II USM. *Kewabotonia nuptirachaelae* second dress from left, worn by Lizzy, while twirling. © Chris Chambers¹¹ or unknown assistant, 2018, all rights reserved.
 - **Page:** See Beaumont (2018a)
 - **SHA2-256:** 631592f926a502692fdc21802c721d1d6da2795a150e63e4fdce14515530ca2f
 - **Raw image URLs**
 - * **Original:** <https://sewprettyful.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/08/0412-ra.jpg>

4.6.4 *Kewabotonia sarae*

Kewabotonia sarae Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Holotype: *Sarah SC.12274KS* — Photograph. 768×960. EXIF metadata stripped. *Kewabotonia sarae* wb. Sarah’s S.C., 2018. © Sarah’s Sewing Chronicles, 2018, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Sarah’s S.C. (2018)
- **SHA2-256:** b5bca18b6114bca9db8de2c1c78acea3fd0622d42df449064636d241c571bbf1
- **Raw image URLs:**

¹⁰We did not assign the letters KN as the image *Rachael 0063* contains five separate dresses, which warrant a taxonomic treatment in their own paper.

¹¹Not explicitly stated in EXIF, but inferred from metadata

- **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260320064630/https://instagram.fmnl35-1.fna.fbcdn.net/v/t51.82787-15/627696672_18327776389174806_2043516935416512274_n.jpg?stp=dst-jpg_e35_tt6&_nc_cat=111&ig_cache_key=MTgyOTI2Mjg0MDUwMzIzMzQzMg%3D%3D.3-ccb7-5&ccb=7-5&_nc_sid=58cdad&efg=eyJ2ZW5jb2RlX3RhZyI6InhwaWRzLjc2OHg5NjAuc2RyLkMzIn0%3D&_nc_ohc=aBa1bCRWqhQ7kNvwHCA36c&_nc_oc=AdounD-lxRYEUHB1gwNxnWn3lTjUgBA49qiqQ8f6EWCrLU6Slz-a16ZA6hndHbhEc&_nc_ad=z-m&_nc_cid=0&_nc_zt=23&_nc_ht=instagram.fmnl35-1.fna&_nc_gid=Bt9fr8_x0I07PnVZ-pwtCA&_nc_ss=7a30f&oh=00_Afzn7zG3lzQloMNPZkZnxpfWDDPP-bQ0HvtoS4XKEREa_tA&oe=69C2ACFA

Description: Shallow angle V-neck, curving medially. Bilateral single straps. Skirt terminates superior to knee. **Fabric.** Unknown material. Light cyan background, floral, yellow flowers, green leaves. No known correspondence to botanical taxa.

Etymology: *Sarah* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

Specimens examined: See holotype information.

4.6.5 *Kewabotonia zingibera*

Kewabotonia zingibera Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Holotype: *Gingerthread 0212KZ* — Photograph. 1200×1800. EXIF metadata stripped; exposure, f-stop, lens foc. len unknown. United Kingdom. Ventral full-body view. Tied hair. Arms spread laterally. *Kewabotonia zingibera* wb. *Gingerthread*, 2018. © Jen Walker or unknown photographer, 2018, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Walker (2018).
- **SHA2-256:** b4d1008027f701f3b22f523bdc3796e64a0cb99ddb17cfd27c186d3d79849bc4.
- **Raw image URLs**
 - **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0725/7833/5029/files/IMG_0212.jpg
 - **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20240921120539/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0725/7833/5029/files/IMG_0212.jpg

Description: Shallow angle V-neck. Bilateral single straps. Lack of ventral medial button row. Sleeves typical to that of *Kewoidea* and level with bodice. Skirt terminates superior to knee. Left strap fully plain black ventrally, right strap features two dots ventrally. **Fabric.** Atelier Brunette “Stardust Night” double gauze. Black background, low-density white dots.

Etymology: Feminine form of Latin *zingiberi* (“ginger”) from the wearer’s alias, Gingerthread Girl.

Specimens examined: See holotype information.

4.7 Genus *Kewasalia*

Kewasalia gen. nov.

Diagnosis: Lack of ventral medial button row, two legs bifurcating, and non-descent from the Portobello trouser pattern.

4.7.1 *Kewasalia pimsia*

Kewasalia pimsia sp. nov.

Holotype: *Pimsy 0001KP* — Photograph. 801×1184. EXIF metadata stripped; exposure, f-stop, lens foc. len unknown. Screenshotted by Chang-Smith, inferred from filename. Unknown location. Ventral view. Subject’s head is to her right. Left strap (wearer’s perspective) slightly obscured by ventrally positioned hair. Legs slightly crossed, obscuring medial interlimb space. *Kewasalia pimsia* wb. @pimsyfaitdestrucs, c. 2018. © unknown, unknown year, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Chang-Smith (2018).
- **SHA2-256:** 3a1763dad87fa6f2dc2edef01c20db87e5e65f2f4f0e6e46bee83ce3ba49e7d0.
- **Raw image URLs**

- **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0725/7833/5029/files/Screen-Shot-2018-08-07-at-13_20_04.jpg
- **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260315221454/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0725/7833/5029/files/Screen-Shot-2018-08-07-at-13_20_04.jpg

Description: Fabric of unknown material, similar appearance to [Ankara print](#). **Fabric.** Pattern consists of multiple square regions divided by vertical bands of dark blue background with white diamonds. Square regions consist of three distinct patterns. Pattern 1, red two-spiral galaxy-like shape on dark blue background. Pattern 2, dark-blue two-spiral galaxy-like shape on mostly gold background. Pattern 3, diamond split into four segments, white borders, against background of repeating dark red–light red–yellow pattern. Medial area of bodice features alternating pattern 2 and 3, while lateral area alternates between 1 and 3. Trousers alternate 1 and 3 ventrally, and 2 and 3 laterally in alternating order. No proof of explicit descent from Portobello.

Etymology: *pimsia* is derived from the wearer’s Instagram handle, @pimsyfaitdestrucs.

Specimens examined: See holotype information.

4.8 Genus *Kewisia*

Kewisia Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Diagnosis: Presence of ventral medial button row, bilateral single straps, and sleeves lateral to the upper arm.

4.8.1 *Kewisia bernicae*

Kewisia bernicae Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Holotype: *Bernice* 37957KB — Photograph. 655×980. EXIF metadata stripped; exposure, f-stop, lens foc. len unknown. Published 2020-04-02. United States, California, San Francisco Bay Area. Ventral view. Hair mostly positioned dorsally, with slight amount of hair obscuring left strap ventrally. *Kewisia bernicae* wb. Bernice, 2020; © Bernice or unknown photographer, 2020, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Bernice (2020)
- **SHA2-256:** f6b6caff6c4e25c48fe6fb5320fbe9119704bed364869b8409b84670ac2af642
- **Raw image URLs**
 - **Original:** <https://cdn.minerva.com/feed/original/image-sa-1031540-1000312-37957.jpg>
 - **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260317204805/https://cdn.minerva.com/feed/original/image-sa-1031540-1000312-37957.jpg>

Description: Shallow angle V-neck. Bilateral single straps. Sleeves typical to that of *Kewoidea* and level with bodice. Bodice shortened by 19 mm (0.75 in), skirt shortened by 38 mm (1.5 in), due to Bernice’s height of 156 cm (5 ft 1 in). **Buttons.** 12 buttons, four on bodice, eight on skirt, divergence from typical 15 buttons. Four thread holes, white dome buttons. Button size more typical of shirts (*Camibotonia*). **Fabric.** Lady McElroy Amerilis Cotton Lawn. White background, floral, stylized depictions of tulips (*Tulipa* L.). Four distinct cuts of fabric inferred from abrupt pattern changes, converging between fourth and fifth button.

Etymology: *Bernice* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

Remarks:

- Instagram specimens exist for *K. bernicae*, but due to the instability and non-reproducibility of image retrievals from Facebook’s CDN, as discussed in Section 4.3.3, we have decided to prioritize reproducibility for *Kewisia bernicae*.
- Minerva processes JPG images using gd-jpeg v1.0, with quality set to 100; CREATOR: gd-jpeg v1.0 (using IJG JPEG v62), quality = 100.
- In Bernice (2020), Bernice writes that her husband is Dutch, and as a result, prefers fabrics with tulips.
- Bernice also reported that some of the images showed the red pencil marks she had placed to mark buttonhole locations; she washed the dress, ironed it, and retook photographs.

Specimens examined:

- Holotype.
- **Bernice 48621KB** — Photograph. 735×980. EXIF metadata stripped; exposure, f-stop, lens foc. len unknown. Published 2020-04-02. United States, California, San Francisco Bay Area. Ventral side of dress laid out on wood table. Image truncates medial portions of shoulder strap. © Bernice or unknown photographer, 2020, all rights reserved.
 - **Page:** See Bernice (2020)
 - **SHA2-256:** be388a4ba51c7e8544cba5f091615195410d009735da2704dc49fd9db7884d1e
 - **Raw image URLs**
 - * **Original:** <https://cdn.minerva.com/feed/original/image-sa-1031540-1000312-48621.jpg>
 - * **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260317211238/https://cdn.minerva.com/feed/original/image-sa-1031540-1000312-48621.jpg>

4.8.2 *Kewisia evae*

Kewisia evae Lemuria, 2026

Holotype: *Eva 3318KE* — Photograph. 3024×4032. EXIF metadata stripped; exposure, f-stop, lens foc. len unknown. Published 2018-09-18. London, United Kingdom. Ventral (front) view. Hair positioned dorsally. © Kate Eva or unknown photographer, 2018, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Eva (2018b).
- **SHA2-256:** 95da481e925293acde9fab746a0ca97ca64366726218958b9bb76e5cfafa7502
- **Raw image URLs**
 - **Original:** https://kateevadesigns.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/09/img_3318.jpg
 - **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260314183108/https://kateevadesigns.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/09/img_3318.jpg

Description: Shallow angle V-neck. Bilateral single straps. Sleeves typical to that of *Kewoidea* and level with bodice. Skirt terminates inferior to knee. Ventral medial row of 13 buttons. 4 on bodice, 8 on skirt, single button at bodice-skirt seam. **Fabric.** Blue linen, plain. Fabrics Galore.

Etymology: *Eva* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

Remarks:

- Eva reported difficulty in accurately photographing the color of *Kewisia evae*. She describes it as “somewhere between a smurf and the Victoria Line”, and “lighter than a cobalt blue but still quite bright”.
- *Kewisia evae* was first described in Lemuria (2026), but it was shortened for brevity. We describe it here in more detail.

Specimens examined: See holotype information.

4.8.3 *Kewisia fionae*

Kewisia fionae Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Holotype: *Parker 0001KF* — Photograph. 1536×2048. EXIF metadata stripped; exposure, f-stop, lens foc. len unknown. Original 2018-06-03. London, United Kingdom. Ventral view. Hair positioned dorsally. © Fiona Parker or unknown photographer, 2018, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Parker (2018)
- **SHA2-256:** bd626b8a6f1310021d4ff6a1660814af1677ab1354e2fe17dfaca8f4c113d893
- **Raw image URLs**
 - **Original:** https://blogger.googleusercontent.com/img/b/R29vZ2xl/AVvXsEimpa9buEQSTCOXcTc4UUSCbSNK_KdN57fjmXpUOxb9rUApekLFckiR44QXxCQAt0oOQiPFKUA3mb7f3HZ3vJU92gu1aFPa0IuSeCABx3J03NQSo6GH2eh0ViuGiKnOFMBZSIiz0KfFLQ/s0/Floral+Viscose+Kew+Dress+Front.jpg=s0?imgmax=0
 - **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260317141612/https://blogger.googleusercontent.com/img/b/R29vZ2xl/AVvXsEimpa9buEQSTCOXcTc4UUSCbSNK_KdN57fjmXpUOxb9rUApekLFckiR44QXxCQAt0oOQiPFKUA3mb7f3HZ3vJU92gu1aFPa0IuSeCABx3J03NQSo6GH2eh0ViuGiKnOFMBZSIiz0KfFLQ/s0/Floral+Viscose+Kew+Dress+Front.jpg=s0?imgmax=0

Description: Shallow angle V-neck. Bilateral single straps. Sleeves typical to that of *Kewoidea* and level with bodice. Skirt terminates inferior to knee. Ventral medial row of 15 buttons, solid black with two thread holes, white thread, sourced from The Cloth House on Berwick Street. Straps shortened by 2.5 cm (1 in). Bust cut at size 8, graded to 10 towards transpyloric plane. **Fabric.** Dahlia viscose crepe, from the company Til The Sun Goes Down, operated by Andree Holden.¹² Floral pattern, black, yellow, and white.

Etymology: *Fiona* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

Remarks:

- Parker purchased the pattern from Chang-Smith herself at the Great British Sewing Bee in January 2018, and began work on the dress by July 2018. In Spring 2018, Andree gifted Parker 1.5 meters of the fabric, 138 cm wide.

Specimens examined: See holotype information.

4.8.4 *Kewisia genyae*

Kewisia genyae sp. nov.

Holotype: *Genya* 2023.0004KG — Photograph. 1920×2560. EXIF metadata stripped. Ventral view. Ventral view. Inferior most two buttons unfastened. *Kewisia genyae* wb. *Genya* (W/2026 F2), 2023. © *Genya* or unknown photographer, 2023, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Chang-Smith (2026)
- **SHA2-256:** c5896da2fc77396abdec02d0fd35c3254e536c334f886c2e3cb8a312a0bf2016
- **Raw image URLs:**
 - **Original:** <https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/products/Genya-4-scaled.jpg?v=1677871708>
 - **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260320191618/https://www.ninalee.co.uk/cdn/shop/products/Genya-4-scaled.jpg?v=1677871708>

Description: Bilateral straps, considerably more medial. Shallow angle V neck. Strap neckline curves medially, with abrupt straight line laterally, roughly 45°. **Buttons.** Ventral medial button row. Buttons on wearer's left. 15 buttons. **Fabric.** Emerald-green, plain, unknown material.

Etymology: *Genya* (from the filename) + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

4.8.5 *Kewisia kristinae*

Kewisia kristinae Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Holotype: *Lehrer* 2018.12320KK — Photograph. 1080×1350. EXIF metadata stripped. Sourced from Meta CDN, original URL non-permanent. Ventral view, *Lehrer* looking down. *Kewisia kristinae* wb. *Lehrer*, 2018. © Kristin *Lehrer*, 2018, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See *Lehrer* (2018a).
- **SHA2-256:** f37209aae5875c28c61f718c51d5752c70e58c8e1b7b62cf147966e3d3971769
- **Raw image URLs:**
 - **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260319132608/https://instagram.fmnl35-1.fna.fbcdn.net/v/t51.2885-15/37916165_271939026870446_3584395751792312320_n.jpg?stp=dst-jpg_e35_tt6&_nc_cat=104&ig_cache_key=MTgzNTc5NTc1OTQ2Mzg1MDg1Nw%3D%3D.3-ccb7-5&ccb=7-5&_nc_sid=58cda&efg=eyJ2ZW5jb2RlX3RhZyI6InhwaWRzLjEwODB4MTM1MC5zZHIuZGVmYXVsdF9pbWFnZS5DMjYJ9&_nc_ohc=ohE9edBqAhwQ7kNvWH1a-vW&_nc_oc=AdoBj2wPIzck737gF5Z2tZoZUXyVGWia74qUPS uFNyExgX3yT0QBe_GqczxysLbQ0qE&_nc_ad=z-m&_nc_cid=0&_nc_zt=23&_nc_ht=instagram.fmnl35-1.fna&_nc_ss=8&oh=00_AfyJ92sFgYXkhTPQ4ZxPIIWGP6khWt6K3IJTf2ImxlRq1g&oe=69C1DBC8

Description: Shallow angle V-neck. Bilateral single straps. Sleeves typical to that of *Kewoidea* and level with bodice. Skirt terminates superior to knee. **Buttons.** Ventral medial row of 15 buttons. Buttons reflective, two thread holes, floral decorations. Background brownish in color. Black thread sewn through. Thread hole alignment variable,

¹²Also known as *Andree Hansen*; inconsistent names observed.

thread line of second button est. 20°. **Fabric.** Black fabric. Floral patterns, featuring ferns (botanical division Polypodiophyta and class Polypodiopsida Cronquist, Takht. & W.Zimm.)

Etymology: *Kristin* + *-ae* feminine genitive suffix.

Remarks

- No method of reliably reproducible video downloads is known.
- On March 19, 2026, we visited Lehrer's Instagram page using Imginn to retrieve photographic evidence. Instagram can now be considered a reproducible source when Save Page Now is used to submit CDN URLs.

Specimens examined:

- Holotype.
- **Yarngasm 281** — YouTube video. *Yarngasm* ep. 281, "There's Been Spinning". 00h39m17.408s. 854×480, 30fps. 48KHz Opus stereo audio. **Encoder:** Lavf60.16.100. **YouTube ID:** 066xjOf4DhM. Ventral and lateral view. Subject is mostly seated, but at 00h20m48s, stands up to show ventral medial button row and lateral seams. Uploaded 2018-08-03. *Kewisia kristinae* wb. Lehrer, 2018. © Kristin Lehrer, 2018, all rights reserved.
- **Lehrer 2018.25504KK** — Photograph. 1080×1350. EXIF metadata stripped. Sourced from Meta CDN, original URL non-permanent. Dorsal view, truncated at medial point of skirt vertically and wearer's right edge of skirt. *Kewisia kristinae* wb. Lehrer, 2018. © Kristin Lehrer, 2018, all rights reserved.
 - **Page:** See Lehrer (2018a)
 - **SHA2-256:** c5dbd79fe03d2f3ebf40cbe06340e785aa141f2ffa0472fd7c04ec4b7277bd35
 - **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260319132612/https%3A//instagram.fmnl35-1.fna.fbcdn.net/v/t51.2885-15/37316534_1166569746843394_2798195026117525504_n.jpg?stp%3Ddst-jpg_e35_tt6%26_nc_cat%3D102%26ig_cache_key%3DMTgzNTc5NTc4MjcwODc1MjA0Nw%3D%3D.3-ccb7-5%26ccb%3D7-5%26_nc_sid%3D58cdad%26efg%3DeyJ2ZW5jb2RlX3RhZyI6InhwaWRzLjEwODB4MTM1MC5zZHIuZGVmYXVsdF9pbWFnZS5DMjY9%26_nc_ohc%3Dd85t6RYe_YQ7kNvwEYfGjO%26_nc_oc%3DAdqVnv2wBUDK-OaR7q2-a8GQq3dheknmR6XeqvFbD3WeW7jvJvHgVWgQpBd_ngvb5WQ%26_nc_ad%3Dz-m%26_nc_cid%3D0%26_nc_zt%3D23%26_nc_ht%3Dinstagram.fmnl35-1.fna%26_nc_ss%3D8%26oh%3D00_Afzkd-5EzthnKYwiyM2RfjC_p-w329JVz5LwT44lgFig%26oe%3D69C1E46A
- **Lehrer 2018.23250KK** — Photograph. 1080×1350. EXIF metadata stripped. Sourced from Meta CDN, original URL non-permanent. Lehrer sitting on chair, facing her right, leaning to her left. *Kewisia kristinae* wb. Lehrer, 2018. © Kristin Lehrer, 2018, all rights reserved.
 - **Page:** See Lehrer (2018a)
 - **SHA2-256:** 77af3ae6d745d43459b95f1c033580d12d6af5795cb1adbe777b497ff68ea302
 - **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260319132619/https://instagram.fmnl35-1.fna.fbcdn.net/v/t51.82787-15/649173683_18316866949301930_5983435372631823250_n.jpg?stp=dst-jpg_e35_tt6&nc_cat=101&ig_cache_key=MTgzNTc5NTc5NDY4NzQ3MDM3MA%3D%3D.3-ccb7-5&ccb=7-5&nc_sid=58cdad&efg=eyJ2ZW5jb2RlX3RhZyI6InhwaWRzLjEwODB4MTM1MC5zZHIuZzIifQ%3D%3D&nc_ohc=vt8MweSfn4UQ7kNvwFuXwxO&nc_oc=AdqWiLnrQ4eBjyJsfOPUKg3yDydnUTjp6-Wgds_khLGVPLhGwivwhhR0mM7ZBDFw&nc_ad=z-m&nc_cid=0&nc_zt=23&nc_ht=instagram.fmnl35-1.fna&nc_gid=IOTvQ_IqLO9tqwOTu7G2Dw&nc_ss=8&oh=00_Afx1FyLjdzYaluIEOFHjy8ZWkfaAT7SzujMBKeWEsrZLQq&oe=69C1C026
- **Lehrer 2018.73568KK** — Photograph. 1080×1350. EXIF metadata stripped. Sourced from Meta CDN, original URL non-permanent. Truncated ventral view. Slanted posture; only right portion of dress visible; black border at edges. *Kewisia kristinae* wb. Lehrer, 2018. © Kristin Lehrer, 2018, all rights reserved.
 - **Page:** See Lehrer (2018a)
 - **SHA2-256:** 1e064765de0c603ba33da49a4cb94728919c751a2dea24202c3a6a3d339f774c
 - **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260319134425/https://instagram.fmnl35-1.fna.fbcdn.net/v/t51.82787-15/650185604_18353554276224234_5543024147734773568_n.jpg?stp=dst-jpg_e35_tt6&nc_cat=103&ig_cache_key=MTgzNTc5NTc5NDI1NTg5NTUxMQ%3D%3D.3-ccb7-5&ccb=7-5&nc_sid=58cdad&efg=eyJ2ZW5jb2RlX3RhZyI6InhwaWRzLjEwODB4MTM1MC5zZHIuZzZMifQ%3D%3D&nc_ohc=Da3G1LZCA8gQ7kNvwFmAk2A&nc_oc=AdoPl_d9ofCr3qFIRNARoqVHnlpazMS_WVZoKjrfOkIz3FaS2qIbQKJH0HTYeKisg_k&nc_ad=z-m&nc_cid=0&nc_zt=23&nc_ht=instagram.fmnl35-1.fna&nc_gid=IOTvQ_IqLO9tqwOTu7G2Dw&nc_ss=8&oh=00_AfxKbEt19a5Jwc6dPho57qoyCcSapjpQrD1hi046QK1Riw&oe=69C1BC19
- **Lehrer 2018.46021KK** — Photograph. 1080×1080. EXIF metadata stripped. Sourced from Meta CDN, original URL non-permanent. Fabric and buttons of *Kewisia kristinae* pre-assembly. © Kristin Lehrer, 2018, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Lehrer (2018a)
- **SHA2-256:** c5dbd79fe03d2f3ebf40cbe06340e785aa141f2ffa0472fd7c04ec4b7277bd35
- **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260319135834/https://instagram.fmnl35-1.fna.fbcdn.net/v/t51.82787-15/625821393_18445416712105093_1850098667885446021_n.jpg?stp=dst-jpg_e35_tt6&nc_cat=107&ig_cache_key=MTc5MjEzMDAwODY3MDUyNjkyNg%3D%3D.3-ccb7-5&ccb=7-5&nc_sid=58cdad&efg=eyJ2ZW5jb2RlX3RhZyI6InhwaWRzLjEwODB4MTA4MC5zZHIuQzMifQ%3D%3D&nc_ohc=D0dHCUirR-UQ7kNvwGKQvd9&nc_oc=AdrFBFl-FmrDDOIYeHiENVJZFoSR9-kMtlzE37JPxSHZtPz6cBOot1aMvHNM6J5280&nc_ad=z-m&nc_cid=0&nc_zt=23&nc_ht=instagram.fmnl35-1.fna&nc_gid=X8WJNR8snzyK4fDawLysg&nc_ss=8&oh=00_AfwiMoVGSiKV4jiwNtmAbqFlN8dm_EjawBycobkLKfXOQ&oe=69C1E1C5
- **Lehrer 0001.G65Z¹³** — YouTube video. *VoolenvVLOG: The Seamstress Tag!*. 00h15m48.648s. 1920×1080, 23.976fps. 48KHz Opus stereo audio. **Encoder:** Lavf60.16.100. **YouTube ID:** C_cpG65ZGyE. Ventral view, subject in center. Frame cuts inferior to fourth button. Uploaded 2018-09-04. *Kewisia kristinae* wb. Lehrer, 2018. © Kristin Lehrer, 2018, all rights reserved. See Lehrer (2018c).

yt-dlp **provenance:** See Section 7.5.

4.8.6 *Kewisia latae*

Kewisia latae Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Holotype: Vic 91147KL — Photograph. 1080×1080. EXIF metadata stripped. Collage compiled by Nina; left panel shows ventral view; hair positioned mostly dorsally with some strands obscuring wearer’s left strap. Right panel shows lateral angled view; hair positioned almost entirely dorsally. *Kewisia latae* wb. Vic.B., 2017. © Vic Broad (@sewvee), 2017, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Vic B. (2017)
- **SHA2-256:** dacf00ee1e4e44c1e96f9675f0e0a13cf104eeb1f3ed7993edb52b4c076bea58
- **Raw image URLs:**
 - **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260322191235/https://instagram.fmnl35-1.fna.fbcdn.net/v/t51.82787-15/621826096_18390981547194776_7014351964259491147_n.jpg?stp=dst-jpg_e35_tt6&nc_cat=111&ig_cache_key=MTU4OTE1NjM2MDI4MDEwMTAyNg%3D%3D.3-ccb7-5&ccb=7-5&nc_sid=58cdad&efg=eyJ2ZW5jb2RlX3RhZyI6InhwaWRzLjEwODB4MTA4MC5zZHIuQzMifQ%3D%3D&nc_ohc=8KeAJuReNDsQ7kNvwGWv1y1&nc_oc=AdpWtE619fPbFBwhaj_TL0sLGwzfnOpPT52Q_Se5fbbSZ70NjHiZxsorUB8SNX62Hpg&nc_ad=z-m&nc_cid=0&nc_zt=23&nc_ht=instagram.fmnl35-1.fna&nc_gid=qD3sWwcVdqigJXrpW9zxHg&nc_ss=7a32e&oh=00_AfyN3DFPiTcKPQaCWqmur-pTiAGgcErO5X7Xz_jZ65W1nw&oe=69C6004B

Description: Shallow angle V neck. Bilateral single straps. Skirt terminates inferior to knee. **Buttons.** Ventral medial button row. 15 visible buttons. Circular, black, unknown number of thread holes; yellow thread seen at center. **Fabric.** Unknown material. African wax print / Ankara print; network of black and white line shapes with central square and four protrusions curved at edges, connected by curved yellow lines. Highly superficial resemblance to ripe bananas (fruit produced by *Musa* L.), but likely unintentional on the part of the designer. Consistent grid of horizontal and vertical spaces with thin black lines curving between black and white line shapes. Horizontally, orange blots on white background, and vertically, moss green blots on white background.

Etymology: Attempted Latinization of the last name Broad to Latin *latus* “broad”, with its feminine form *lata* combined with *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

Remarks: Vic Broad’s account (@sewvee) is private, though imagery of *Kewisia latae* is available on the official Nina Lee Instagram account (@ninaleelondon).

Specimens examined: See holotype information.

4.8.7 *Kewisia lizae*

Kewisia lizae Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

¹³Derived from portion of YouTube alphanumeric video ID.

Holotype: *Liz GCS2018.004KL* — Photograph 1800×2048. PNG. EXIF metadata stripped; exposure, f-stop, lens foc. len unknown. *Kewisia lizae* wb. Liz of G., 2018. Zoomed out angled ventral view. Hair positioned dorsally. Subject interacting with *Ficus carica* L. © Liz of *Girl Can Sew* or unknown photographer, 2018, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Liz of G. (2018)
- **SHA2-256:** 4d0e2020c3e69548761f8881c493e15eb6b52abecdc3ff1ec084c6e6e95888ef
- **Raw image URLs**
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 - **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318201220/https://blogger.googleusercontent.com/img/b/R29vZ2xl/AVvXsEhSRIQVOGfqGiY41H2S3oQjjbDYUBGW3hH2kaKgs32_enX2VI9YLYILKit6V4uXEZWeMrp9px0Jb4WrEUjf_A3JhZzea7eVOs7CmE_U2KJVJ0p0CsvILDsmxuK-eM_zRkevs5Aqw7LxRXA/s1600/kew+dress+fig.png

Description: Shallow angle V-neck. Ventral medial button row. Superior edge of strap slightly inferior to superior edge of bodice. **Buttons.** 14 buttons. Possible 15th button, most inferior, uncertain due to image angles. Yellow, floral-shaped edges, two thread holes, aligned mostly horizontally. Sourced from Walthamstow Market. **Fabric.** Cotton with meadow print, gray/brown background. Grass, flora. Species include but not limited to *Leucanthemum vulgare* Lam., orange flowers most likely *Calendula officinalis* though pistil is white. Pink and orange stylized depictions of *Amanita muscaria*. (L.) Lam. (1783), and *Muscari armeniacum* Leichtlin.

Etymology: *Liz* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

Specimens examined:

- Holotype.
- **Liz GCS2018.001KL** — Photograph 2048×1710. PNG. EXIF metadata stripped; exposure, f-stop, lens foc. len unknown. *Kewisia lizae* wb. Liz of G., 2018. Truncated ventral view, from neckline to sixth button. © Liz of *Girl Can Sew* or unknown photographer, 2018, all rights reserved.
 - **Page:** See Liz of G. (2018)
 - **SHA2-256:** 2917f507f50e9dcfd28ef9c852e9bd93b1278d98922b9e3372b28f6d931719b5
 - **Raw image URLs**
 - * **Original:** https://blogger.googleusercontent.com/img/b/R29vZ2xl/AVvXsEjAfGLBo7XXYtjiIekZCHC_ticdhCwxIQq_hmUru6QuosQ51fk2fFHOWlOj8lPCZIkCqHlw8YwIDUusJ-IFxYv00kEkNP_nZedAOIdbfvUOVujsPzFuqqV4BqTn2tUtaCgbVQUcKWiiVto/s0/kew+close+up.png=s0?imgmax=0
 - * **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318202213/https://blogger.googleusercontent.com/img/b/R29vZ2xl/AVvXsEjAfGLBo7XXYtjiIekZCHC_ticdhCwxIQq_hmUru6QuosQ51fk2fFHOWlOj8lPCZIkCqHlw8YwIDUusJ-IFxYv00kEkNP_nZedAOIdbfvUOVujsPzFuqqV4BqTn2tUtaCgbVQUcKWiiVto/s0/kew+close+up.png=s0?imgmax=0
- **Liz GCS2018.002KL** — Photograph 1264×2048. PNG. EXIF metadata stripped; exposure, f-stop, lens foc. len unknown. *Kewisia lizae* wb. Liz of G., 2018. Zoomed out ventral view. Hair tied, wearer's left strap obscured. Subject looking upward at *Wisteria* L. plant in blue vase. © Liz of *Girl Can Sew* or unknown photographer, 2018, all rights reserved.
 - **Page:** See Liz of G. (2018)
 - **SHA2-256:** 486862f315a8f307bf1691f90577ddc4f21f409d4c2a89b76693942c98db73af
 - **Raw image URLs**
 - * **Original:** https://blogger.googleusercontent.com/img/b/R29vZ2xl/AVvXsEhqmp9LmXbE3UDWakmFKhVMgyJSpnF5tf_1RjFGDceMbZ8grPcLqPGCdEO1n77hL43nK7UgZBbTkKXyTCT_iRKi8EhpD7duJ4XJhwSDwZSOAt8WWlxxazwEIRUOffy7bAShX2ltg2tHMM/s0/kew+dress+wysteria.png=s0?imgmax=0
 - * **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318204902/https://blogger.googleusercontent.com/img/b/R29vZ2xl/AVvXsEhqmp9LmXbE3UDWakmFKhVMgyJSpnF5tf_1RjFGDceMbZ8grPcLqPGCdEO1n77hL43nK7UgZBbTkKXyTCT_iRKi8EhpD7duJ4XJhwSDwZSOAt8WWlxxazwEIRUOffy7bAShX2ltg2tHMM/s0/kew+dress+wysteria.png=s0?imgmax=0
- **Liz GCS2018.003KL** — Photograph 1122×2048. PNG. EXIF metadata stripped; exposure, f-stop, lens foc. len unknown. *Kewisia lizae* wb. Liz of G., 2018. Zoomed out dorsal view. Hair positioned dorsally. Subject interacting with *Wisteria* L. plant in blue vase. © Liz of *Girl Can Sew* or unknown photographer, 2018, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Liz of G. (2018)
- **SHA2-256:** d83d649efb74a7296095e99ca8a871f8942b4f759f943514ce786534a26fbc14
- **Raw image URLs**
 - * **Original:** https://blogger.googleusercontent.com/img/b/R29vZ2xl/AVvXsEh2tKHL-yMVyts7S9-ROPAVKPL_W5VI00Yuox9eM8wV6WFjMKHokyP57lon_jZ1mKPOLsJDX2v56t5ngjQgpd-bW1syGJAZOiqnWSVo51cANw4ZJhVDJEvAI8IddaeB1x0ccwhTGG7yHw/s0/kew+dress+back.png=s0?imgmax=0
 - * **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318202027/https://blogger.googleusercontent.com/img/b/R29vZ2xl/AVvXsEh2tKHL-yMVyts7S9-ROPAVKPL_W5VI00Yuox9eM8wV6WFjMKHokyP57lon_jZ1mKPOLsJDX2v56t5ngjQgpd-bW1syGJAZOiqnWSVo51cANw4ZJhVDJEvAI8IddaeB1x0ccwhTGG7yHw/s0/kew+dress+back.png=s0?imgmax=0

4.8.8 *Kewisia mariae*

Kewisia mariae Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Holotype: *Marie 2451a-KM* — Photograph. 1667×2304. EXIF metadata stripped; exposure, f-stop, lens foc. len unknown. *Kewisia mariae* wb. Marie.K., 2018. Ventral view. Hair positioned dorsally. © Marie Koupparis or unknown photographer, 2018, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Koupparis (2018)
- **SHA2-256:** a992ac2dbb3b55320886a28e9778ef7782f8814aeece9f26145e4504fe3cf23d
- **Raw image URLs**
 - **Original:** https://blogger.googleusercontent.com/img/b/R29vZ2xl/AVvXsEiYDPntuXBiAGWj83JOLH3aTGTEFpo2VGgYgeLT9foDtvpnW2CFbq5JbZ0mZ29jsDbBHQQa61bDCiu-aBxIdJ1tpjRMGG9m-csx8oXVtFgTKadSQ_P_ti_Umu3DkbFG1deGHeL0Q1sD-pY/s0/IMG_2451a.jpg=s0?imgmax=0
 - **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260317191624/https://blogger.googleusercontent.com/img/b/R29vZ2xl/AVvXsEiYDPntuXBiAGWj83JOLH3aTGTEFpo2VGgYgeLT9foDtvpnW2CFbq5JbZ0mZ29jsDbBHQQa61bDCiu-aBxIdJ1tpjRMGG9m-csx8oXVtFgTKadSQ_P_ti_Umu3DkbFG1deGHeL0Q1sD-pY/s0/IMG_2451a.jpg=s0?imgmax=0

Description: Shallow angle V-neck. Ventral medial row of 14 buttons. Bilateral single straps, 3 cm (1.2 in) shorter than pattern. Facing along neckline sewn with 1 cm (0.39 in) seam allowance instead of typical 1.5 cm (0.59 in) for modesty reasons. Skirt terminates around the knee. Size 14. **Buttons.** Peach-colored buttons. Two thread holes, curved square shape, sharp squared funnel towards core. Thread color likely white; no distinct color seen against fabric. **Fabric.** Poly crepe from Sew Me Sunshine. Small white dots scattered on background. Apparent background color on monitor is dark sky blue, though it is described by Marie as teal in real life. Floral print, one distinct type of flower, roots and leaves printed, no fully confident correspondence to botanical species; presumably unknown spp. in *Dianthus* L.; most likely *D. caryophyllus* L. or *D. chinensis* L.

Etymology: *Marie* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

Remarks:

- Marie sewed the dress in 2018, after being invited to the wedding of Amy Scarr (the author of the blog *Almond Rock*; former editor of *Love Sewing*). Marie decreased the seam allowance on the neckline’s facing due to worries about excessive exposure, writing that she is self-conscious about her large bust.

Specimens examined:

- Holotype.
- ***Marie 2456a-KM*** — Photograph. 1686×2122. EXIF metadata stripped; exposure, f-stop, lens foc. len unknown. *Kewisia mariae* wb. Marie.K., 2018. © Marie Koupparis or unknown photographer, 2018, all rights reserved.
 - **Page:** See Koupparis (2018)
 - **SHA2-256:** 7fdb218a3f4aef12478250d7d3b211c1d0a67c09207ce94ee8a63eb72a2972e0
 - **Raw image URLs**
 - * **Original:** https://blogger.googleusercontent.com/img/b/R29vZ2xl/AVvXsEjPcnVgFo0Gq7kVF9ajjaHRQ8OA-_veNUmHJqwrYgZ7Z0cREoqXdn429NYtAfGkxdh82BY0FcrHHmN4DdLR2JdPe0INmN1lXM0ZAhypphenphenObL1YZGGI7rsEoEe06CVQ6b8svqrt10zqT2_N3Ys/s0/IMG_2456a.jpg=s0?imgmax=0

- * **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260317184339/https://blogger.googleusercontent.com/img/b/R29vZ2xl/AVvXsEjPcnVgFo0Gq7kVF9ajjaHRQ80A-_veNUMHJqWRYGz7Z0cREoqXdn429NYtAfGkxdh82BY0FcrHHmN4DdLR2JdPe0INmN1XM0ZAhyphenhyphenObL1YZGGI7rsEoEe06CVQ6b8svqrt1OzqT2_N3Ys/s0/IMG_2456a.jpg=s0?imgmax=0
- **Marie 2468a-KM** — Photograph. 1691×2097. EXIF metadata stripped; exposure, f-stop, lens foc. len unknown. *Kewisia mariae* wb. Marie.K., 2018. Lateral view. Hair positioned both ventrally and dorsally. Right shoulder (wearer's perspective) visible. © Marie Koupparis or unknown photographer, 2018, all rights reserved.
 - **Page:** See Koupparis (2018)
 - **SHA2-256:** 8c5e46a833c832c4d3d53615dfe9a003a5b173efb8e1e408c1c22886268377eb
 - **Raw image URLs**
 - * **Original:** https://blogger.googleusercontent.com/img/b/R29vZ2xl/AVvXsEhZZScKesEClgC_5eowrJ2CdGFDAYrkyRcbDKwc_47LEwOm2mhGDC8tcAqxD4cE9ai3aOmQ1PzE7b0eAtgnHuc4vGWFY6O3rnKSqgwils3ZN859_EzYVOZOghMeFHUusrMuu9G0tp81szs/s0/IMG_2468a.jpg=s0?imgmax=0
 - * **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260317185037/https://blogger.googleusercontent.com/img/b/R29vZ2xl/AVvXsEhZZScKesEClgC_5eowrJ2CdGFDAYrkyRcbDKwc_47LEwOm2mhGDC8tcAqxD4cE9ai3aOmQ1PzE7b0eAtgnHuc4vGWFY6O3rnKSqgwils3ZN859_EzYVOZOghMeFHUusrMuu9G0tp81szs/s0/IMG_2468a.jpg=s0?imgmax=0
- **Marie 2470a-KM** — Photograph. 1675×2144. EXIF metadata stripped; exposure, f-stop, lens foc. len unknown. Dorsal view. Hair positioned dorsally. *Kewisia mariae* wb. Marie.K., 2018. © Marie Koupparis or unknown photographer, 2018, all rights reserved.
 - **Page:** See Koupparis (2018)
 - **SHA2-256:** d10ebe770098763baf c66333adb9e5cb3e73348cbaabf51e99e0f3347887e646
 - **Raw image URLs**
 - * **Original:** https://blogger.googleusercontent.com/img/b/R29vZ2xl/AVvXsEgql5hi-kjKPvkeW6EPpXXPgrMT5xDb2L1vfcOR-nmSgJOKoO6E307JajKyOXa-CQq1N3-TBdCXlnVnBgXyzN-B7GMfgAUfpthtjfhmcq_hwc87SJSPPvIezaLg63meA7JqKcy0jEeRXwac/s0/IMG_2470a.jpg=s0?imgmax=0
 - * **IA:** http://web.archive.org/web/20260317191321/https://blogger.googleusercontent.com/img/b/R29vZ2xl/AVvXsEgql5hi-kjKPvkeW6EPpXXPgrMT5xDb2L1vfcOR-nmSgJOKoO6E307JajKyOXa-CQq1N3-TBdCXlnVnBgXyzN-B7GMfgAUfpthtjfhmcq_hwc87SJSPPvIezaLg63meA7JqKcy0jEeRXwac/s0/IMG_2470a.jpg=s0?imgmax=0
- **Marie 2485KM** — Photograph. 3128×2346. EXIF metadata stripped; exposure, f-stop, lens foc. len unknown. Angled lateral view. Buttons 3–12 visible. *Kewisia mariae* wb. Marie.K., 2018. © Marie Koupparis or unknown photographer, 2018, all rights reserved.
 - **Page:** See Koupparis (2018)
 - **SHA2-256:** b26b958487ab3a10063086f85431eaace3fff18cadbf56655c913f2325620975
 - **Raw image URLs**
 - * **Original:** https://blogger.googleusercontent.com/img/b/R29vZ2xl/AVvXsEgzNsGMTc15tt13dJ9BqC-SWdncvVIOqn4zZOh3SWDN2bK1BdupNHNhz0vxuplWABq-ShlLuXWzqV_D2Q46Umk77vgBv2oFFRfTU3D5WMLAOPYesRBxZrnbrG5vJirOp7SNRMEP9hhEeQ/s0/IMG_2485.jpg=s0?imgmax=0
 - * **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260317191103/https://blogger.googleusercontent.com/img/b/R29vZ2xl/AVvXsEgzNsGMTc15tt13dJ9BqC-SWdncvVIOqn4zZOh3SWDN2bK1BdupNHNhz0vxuplWABq-ShlLuXWzqV_D2Q46Umk77vgBv2oFFRfTU3D5WMLAOPYesRBxZrnbrG5vJirOp7SNRMEP9hhEeQ/s0/IMG_2485.jpg=s0?imgmax=0
- **Marie 2494KM** — Photograph. 2346×3128. EXIF metadata stripped; exposure, f-stop, lens foc. len unknown. Ventral view, laid out on table. © Marie Koupparis or unknown photographer, 2018, all rights reserved.
 - **Page:** See Koupparis (2018)
 - **SHA2-256:** a1ce2b1ee666410ab671b217b926067b0fa7b045d51d30de50cab4112b4168d8
 - **Raw image URLs**
 - * **Original:** https://blogger.googleusercontent.com/img/b/R29vZ2xl/AVvXsEh7KEOSlhev1CSSvTZYGaoZLoqhv2IKlTcnhVGE7snPy_GoqvqLKfjPF70iEO1Y00tkMr3KikP1iDVIoqRpyuCnrGAc67MAKxAAABvtbFAd4olH34USJR4-H52m3BfyGQan3at2Vtcqxmzk/s0/IMG_2494.jpg=s0?imgmax=0
 - * **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260317185718/https://blogger.googleusercontent.com/img/b/R29vZ2xl/AVvXsEh7KEOSlhev1CSSvTZYGaoZLoqhv2IKlTcnhVGE7snPy_GoqvqLKfjPF70iEO1Y00tkMr3KikP1iDVIoqRpyuCnrGAc67MAKxAAABvtbFAd4olH34USJR4-H52m3BfyGQan3at2Vtcqxmzk/s0/IMG_2494.jpg=s0?imgmax=0

4.8.9 *Kewisia modistaflora*

Kewisia modistaflora Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Holotype: *Sally M40C8B-KR* — Photograph. 2048×2048. EXIF metadata stripped. Collage. Left panel ventral view, right panel angled dorsal view, subject on stairs. Hair terminates superior to collarbone. *Kewisia modistaflora* wb. Sally of M., unknown. © Sally of Modista Sewing, unknown, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Sally of M. (2020)
- **SHA2-256:** f51f778838d18bf96f628bca17d327e0363d2b8008e03150e2e1277e5bcc67d8
- **Raw image URLs**
 - **Original:** <https://modistasewing.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/0bcc5ecb-0e67-445d-9415-468f7bf40c8b.jpg>
 - **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260318222032/https://modistasewing.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/0bcc5ecb-0e67-445d-9415-468f7bf40c8b.jpg>

Description: Shallow angle V-neck. Bilateral single straps. Skirt terminates inferior to knee. Shoulder sleeve vertically inverted. **Buttons.** Button count inconclusive due to image quality. **Fabric.** Cotton lawn from Abakhan. Black background. Floral; yellow and pink flowers.

Etymology: *Modista* + Pseudo-Latin *flora* “flower”¹⁴, from Latin *Flora*, the goddess of flowers.

Specimens examined: See holotype information.

4.8.10 *Kewisia modistarubera*

Kewisia modistarubera Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Holotype: *Sally M8644KR* — Photograph. 1241×3353. Exposure: 1/33s. F-stop: 1.8. Focal: 3.99 mm. ISO: unknown. Camera: iPhone 7. Lens: iPhone 7 back camera 3.99mm f/1.8. Ventral view, mirror selfie. *Kewisia modistarubera* wb. Sally of M., 2019. © Sally of Modista Sewing, 2019, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Sally of M. (2020)
- **SHA2-256:** d94142e9d1d2e4875b26f3917df933bfce1c96e5e0e04679ca3322e9eb16ff92
- **Raw image URLs**
 - **Original:** https://modistasewing.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/img_8644.jpg
 - **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318220504/https://modistasewing.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/img_8644.jpg

Description: Shallow angle V-neck. Bilateral single straps. Skirt terminates slightly inferior to knee. **Buttons.** Ventral medial row of 6 buttons. Circular, two thread holes, horizontal. Three on bodice, three on skirt. **Fabric.** Red stretch jacquard from Abakhan. Raised embroidery.

Etymology: *Modista* + Latin *ruber* “red”, feminine form *rubra*, accidentally corrupted to *rubera*.

Remarks: After Sally wore her *K. modistaflora* to a 2019 wedding in Scotland, the dress proved popular amongst her friends; and one of them requested a red Kew dress from her. She was unable to photograph the friend wearing it, leaving the mirror selfie as the only available type.

Specimens examined: See holotype information.

4.8.11 *Kewisia rachaelae*

Kewisia rachaelae Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Holotype: *Rachael 2018.KL20* — Photograph. 2652×4031. Exposure: 1/60s. F-stop: 1.7. Focal: 4.20 mm. ISO: unknown. Lens: unknown. Camera: SM-G950F. Ventral view. Wearer’s left arm placed on bodice, inferior to bodice–skirt line. *Kewisia rachaelae* wb. Rachael, 2018. © Rachael Beaumont or unknown photographer, 2018, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Beaumont (2018b)

¹⁴The actual Latin word for “flower” is *flos*.

- **SHA2-256:** 81942cc72cfce9de1edca8fa6309b02bf8d9bd3927a4422f23863d8b7871c51d
- **Raw image URLs**
 - **Original:** <https://sewprettyful.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/03/nina-lee-kew-dress-20.jpg>

Description: Shallow angle V-neck. Bilateral single straps. **Buttons.** 12 buttons, 5 on bodice, 7 on skirt. Fabric covered. Bodice size 10, with 1 in (2.54 cm) bust adjustment. 1.5 cm seam allowance. Skirt terminates parallel to knee, shortened by 3.25 in (8.25 cm). **Fabric.** Lavender background. Floral. Plants include but are not limited to *Adiantum capillus-veneris* L. (maidenhair fern), *Hydrangea macrophylla* (Thunb.) Ser. (bigleaf hydrangea). On sleeves, stylized bird most similar to *Irena puella* (Latham, 1790), the Asian fairy-bluebird.

Etymology: *Rachael* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

Remarks:

- Due to content negotiation issues between the Wayback Machine’s crawler and Rachael’s site (where images return HTML previews instead), we recommend these links for verifying the archive:
 - https://archive.org/details/archiveteam_archivebot_go_20260320094602_3d45c6e0
 - Other Archiveteam archives for Rachael’s blog may be indexed at <https://archive.fart.website/archivebot/viewer/domain/sewprettyful.wordpress.com>.

Specimens examined:

- Holotype.
- **Rachael 2018.KL05** — Photograph. 1934×3497. Exposure: 1/50s. F-stop: 1.7. Focal: 4.20 mm. ISO: unknown. Lens: unknown. Camera: SM-G950F. Angled lateral view, wearer’s left. *Kewisia rachaelae* wb. Rachael, 2018. © Rachael Beaumont or unknown photographer, 2018, all rights reserved.
 - **Page:** See Beaumont (2018b)
 - **SHA2-256:** 16b1992272a5f1b39d7d3d26d2c8d56684c1de369c3d8a28bc34288ed8eb1d09
 - **Raw image URLs**
 - * **Original:** <https://sewprettyful.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/03/nina-lee-kew-dress-5.jpg>
- **Rachael 2018.KL08** — Photograph. 1955×3956. Exposure: 1/50s. F-stop: 1.7. Focal: 4.20 mm. ISO: unknown. Lens: unknown. Camera: SM-G950F. Dorsal view. Hair positioned ventrally. *Kewisia rachaelae* wb. Rachael, 2018. © Rachael Beaumont or unknown photographer, 2018, all rights reserved.
 - **Page:** See Beaumont (2018b)
 - **SHA2-256:** 6032dc87d20e92423d5c75cf0dd22449f7eb9eceb326a1bcb5dcd0c268a3f457
 - **Raw image URLs**
 - * **Original:** <https://sewprettyful.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/03/nina-lee-kew-dress-8.jpg>
- **Rachael 2018.KL10** — Photograph. 1758×3356. Exposure: 1/50s. F-stop: 1.7. Focal: 4.20 mm. ISO: unknown. Lens: unknown. Camera: SM-G950F. Angled ventral view, wearer’s right. *Kewisia rachaelae* wb. Rachael, 2018. © Rachael Beaumont or unknown photographer, 2018, all rights reserved.
 - **Page:** See Beaumont (2018b)
 - **SHA2-256:** 058879679b2ee772611cf037226ac87f37a7cffcaeb029669e339be206f8486f
 - **Raw image URLs**
 - * **Original:** <https://sewprettyful.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/03/nina-lee-kew-dress-10.jpg>
- **Rachael 2018.KL11** — Photograph. 1952×3333. Exposure: 1/50s. F-stop: 1.7. Focal: 4.20 mm. ISO: unknown. Lens: unknown. Camera: SM-G950F. Slightly angled ventral view. Hair positioned ventrally and obscuring straps on wearer’s left. *Kewisia rachaelae* wb. Rachael, 2018. © Rachael Beaumont or unknown photographer, 2018, all rights reserved.
 - **Page:** See Beaumont (2018b)
 - **SHA2-256:** d30c31b86de13d7c0a4dc09cf6d735da4821a284f230d190b747022b60c24654
 - **Raw image URLs**
 - * **Original:** <https://sewprettyful.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/03/nina-lee-kew-dress-11.jpg>

- **Rachael 2018.KL13** — Photograph. 3024×4032. Exposure: 1/50s. F-stop: 1.7. Focal: 4.20 mm. ISO: unknown. Lens: unknown. Camera: SM-G950F. Slightly angled ventral view, wearer’s left, tighter crop. *Kewisia rachaelae* wb. Rachael, 2018. © Rachael Beaumont or unknown photographer, 2018, all rights reserved.
 - **Page:** See Beaumont (2018b)
 - **SHA2-256:** eac1a6b5a97f262ff1c9600b1c896ee873c258e41488456a8090f087641f961e
 - **Raw image URLs**
 - * **Original:** <https://sewprettyful.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/03/nina-lee-kew-dress-13.jpg>
- **Rachael 2018.KL15** — Photograph. 2091×2683. Exposure: 1/50s. F-stop: 1.7. Focal: 4.20 mm. ISO: unknown. Lens: unknown. Camera: SM-G950F. Ventral view of fabric, buttons 4–8. *Kewisia rachaelae* wb. Rachael, 2018. © Rachael Beaumont or unknown photographer, 2018, all rights reserved.
 - **Page:** See Beaumont (2018b)
 - **SHA2-256:** 21272992a994272686afd4c56f97b4d85588b7791c5fd463e8f5febfd4d9aefc
 - **Raw image URLs**
 - * **Original:** <https://sewprettyful.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/03/nina-lee-kew-dress-15.jpg>
- **Rachael 2018.KL16** — Photograph. 2134×2990. Exposure: 1/50s. F-stop: 1.7. Focal: 4.20 mm. ISO: unknown. Lens: unknown. Camera: SM-G950F. Truncated lateral view, wearer’s left, shoulder emphasized. *Kewisia rachaelae* wb. Rachael, 2018. © Rachael Beaumont or unknown photographer, 2018, all rights reserved.
 - **Page:** See Beaumont (2018b)
 - **SHA2-256:** 9a3beb36341ad12a37e3ad41165a661740ebe4b81c86c278e627a43088d9be7f
 - **Raw image URLs**
 - * **Original:** <https://sewprettyful.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/03/nina-lee-kew-dress-16.jpg>
- **Rachael 2018.KL17** — Photograph. 2876×3337. Exposure: 1/50s. F-stop: 1.7. Focal: 4.20 mm. ISO: unknown. Lens: unknown. Camera: SM-G950F. Truncated dorsal view, subject likely has arms crossed ventrally. *Kewisia rachaelae* wb. Rachael, 2018. © Rachael Beaumont or unknown photographer, 2018, all rights reserved.
 - **Page:** See Beaumont (2018b)
 - **SHA2-256:** 6ae8e3847828e6027db7a211ee7a77584b7d7a88eff99845bf4d67f06b5336ec
 - **Raw image URLs**
 - * **Original:** <https://sewprettyful.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/03/nina-lee-kew-dress-17.jpg>
- **Rachael 2018.KL19** — Photograph. 2518×4032. Exposure: 1/60s. F-stop: 1.7. Focal: 4.20 mm. ISO: unknown. Lens: unknown. Camera: SM-G950F. Ventral view, zoomed out, subject standing straight, hair positioned dorsally. *Kewisia rachaelae* wb. Rachael, 2018. © Rachael Beaumont or unknown photographer, 2018, all rights reserved.
 - **Page:** See Beaumont (2018b)
 - **SHA2-256:** 813e05079ef6ace0692a867eaa489504ae8edd030358333d75f75d269fdc8c2
 - **Raw image URLs**
 - * **Original:** <https://sewprettyful.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/03/nina-lee-kew-dress-19.jpg>

4.8.12 *Kewisia reginarunae*

Kewisia reginarunae Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Holotype: *Alice 88719KR* — Photograph. 1334×2000. EXIF metadata stripped. Ventral view. Hair positioned ventrally, wearer’s right strap obscured. *Kewisia reginarunae* wb. Alice.W., 2021. © Alice Wang or unknown photographer, 2021, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Wang (2021)
- **SHA2-256:** 94067b4af92cf45d7aaf9432f81c9e6a5c1093c3ef49c8b055145385551d2579
- **Raw image URLs**
 - **Original:** <https://cdn.minerva.com/feed/original/image-sa-1066483-1000155-88719.jpg>
 - **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260320181642/https://cdn.minerva.com/feed/original/image-sa-1066483-1000155-88719.jpg>

Description: Shallow angle V neck. Based on outdated measurements, size 6, graded to size 8 at waist. Bodice shortened by 2.54 cm (1 in). **Buttons.** Ventral medial row of 13 buttons. **Fabric.** Viscose from Art Gallery Fabrics. Blue background, floral, no known correspondence to botanical taxa.

Etymology: Latin *regina* “queen” + *runa* “dart” + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

Remarks:

- She purchased the pattern in July 2019, then printed it in April 2020, and by January 2021, cut the viscose to create the dress. She first began wearing it in February 2021.
- Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, Alice’s physical activity was significantly reduced, which caused her body mass to increase. As a result, when she wore it, Alice wrote in her blog post that she felt “quite restricted in it”. However, it still fit; no major gaps emerged between the buttons.

Specimens examined:

- Holotype.
- **Alice 94531KR** — Photograph. 1334×2000. EXIF metadata stripped. Dorsal view. Hair positioned dorsally, terminating superior to sleeve. Straps not obscured. *Kewisia reginarunae* wb. Alice W., 2021. © Alice of *Queen of Darts*, 2021, all rights reserved.
 - **Page:** See Wang (2021)
 - **SHA2-256:** d8ac52970bd74dfd6d49c6ff255c1796b6975d68179a306808f5adec2e12158b
 - **Raw image URLs**
 - * **Original:** <https://cdn.minerva.com/feed/original/image-sa-1066483-1000155-94531.jpg>
 - * **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260320181638/https://cdn.minerva.com/feed/original/image-sa-1066483-1000155-94531.jpg>
- **Alice 33300KR** — Photograph. 1334×2000. EXIF metadata stripped. Angled ventral view, hair positioned laterally, straps not obscured. *Kewisia reginarunae* wb. Alice W., 2021. © Alice of *Queen of Darts*, 2021, all rights reserved.
 - **Page:** See Wang (2021)
 - **SHA2-256:** 095dfeea27b6c77408c1b0abff70aa1188a3e5b47091bcea7d8d4cc96751e8f1
 - **Raw image URLs**
 - * **Original:** <https://cdn.minerva.com/feed/original/image-sa-1066483-1000155-33300.jpg>
 - * **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260320181644/https://cdn.minerva.com/feed/original/image-sa-1066483-1000155-33300.jpg>
- **Alice 29682KR** — Photograph. 1334×2000. EXIF metadata stripped. Left lateral view. Left elbow extended out. *Kewisia reginarunae* wb. Alice W., 2021. © Alice of *Queen of Darts*, 2021, all rights reserved.
 - **Page:** See Wang (2021)
 - **SHA2-256:** e97a99a05cc41f27c5f3bf414123b2933ef4a81e8dfa5b3a7f3a23b61e36066a
 - **Raw image URLs**
 - * **Original:** <https://cdn.minerva.com/feed/original/image-sa-1066483-1000155-29682.jpg>
 - * **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260320181636/https://cdn.minerva.com/feed/original/image-sa-1066483-1000155-29682.jpg>
- **Alice 18651KR** — Photograph. 1334×2000. EXIF metadata stripped. Dress on red mannequin, truncated ventral view from first to eighth buttons. © Alice of *Queen of Darts*, 2021, all rights reserved.
 - **Page:** See Wang (2021)
 - **SHA2-256:** 0bfaa8acf7e17c8f07b86cdad15be8c77783ba15515e12da12454ab1a4f17af1
 - **Raw image URLs**
 - * **Original:** <https://cdn.minerva.com/feed/original/image-sa-1066483-1000155-18651.jpg>
 - * **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260320181702/https://cdn.minerva.com/feed/original/image-sa-1066483-1000155-18651.jpg>
- **Alice 27962KR** — Photograph. 1334×2000. EXIF metadata stripped. Dress on red mannequin, angled ventral view of sleeve and strap. © Alice of *Queen of Darts*, 2021, all rights reserved.
 - **Page:** See Wang (2021)
 - **SHA2-256:** ca0b7444873272bdc8262139cd20fdf871fb29523a88a407e5a84dd0d4de4fb3
 - **Raw image URLs**
 - * **Original:** <https://cdn.minerva.com/feed/original/image-sa-1066483-1000155-27962.jpg>
 - * **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260320181712/https://cdn.minerva.com/feed/original/image-sa-1066483-1000155-27962.jpg>

[sa-1066483-1000155-27962.jpg](#)

4.8.13 *Kewisia sarae*

Kewisia sarae Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Holotype: *Sarah D-2019.44536KS* — Photograph. 718×980. EXIF metadata stripped. United Kingdom. Ventral view. Subject holding glass in left hand, partially obscuring left strap. *Kewisia sarae* wb. Sarah.D., 2019.

- **Page:** See sewsarahstitch (2019)
- **SHA2-256:** 810e225bc5de583db9c1ee64e97bcb00ff9280b7e0b5042923c1c4f736958000
- **Raw image URLs**
 - **Original:** <https://cdn.minerva.com/feed/original/image-sa-1022445-1000882-44536.jpg>
 - **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260322150632/https://cdn.minerva.com/feed/original/image-sa-1022445-1000882-44536.jpg>

Description: Bilateral single straps. Size 12. High-low hem. **Buttons.** Ventral medial button row. Minimum upper bound of button count 10, based on holotype visibility. Black wooden buttons from eBay. **Fabric.** Cotton poplin fabric, with poppies (*Papaveraceae* Juss.). Black background. Poppy flowers at high density, roots included. Pattern discontinuity at bodice–skirt seam and across ventral medial button row.

Etymology *Sarah* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

Remarks: The holotype is of low-resolution, and we could not identify the exact number of buttons. The drape of the skirt also obscured the inferior portions of the button row.

4.9 Genus *Kewpepla*

Kewpepla Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Diagnosis: Distinguished from *Kewthea* by lack of skirt.

4.9.1 *Kewpepla lornae*

Kewpepla lornae Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Holotype: *Rothery 613D.KL* — Photograph. EXIF metadata stripped; exposure, f-stop, lens foc. len. unknown. United Kingdom. *Kewpepla lornae* on wooden hanger held by Rothery. © Lorna Rothery or Lorna Malkin (name seen in EXIF data; see Section 5.1), 2020, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Rothery (2020a).
- **SHA2-256:** 827245bb3491960ea11f5a40fc7e4b966c335abef490c1ddc2cff5067ccc5522
- **Raw image URLs**
 - **Original:** <https://lornarothery.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/05/7bd2d058-6968-4c5f-8163-c195a33c613d.jpg>
 - **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260317104813/https://lornarothery.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/05/7bd2d058-6968-4c5f-8163-c195a33c613d.jpg>

Description: V-neck at approx. 47° angle. Sleeve terminates superior to arm. Distal lateral fabric gathering. Ventral medial row of 4 buttons. **Fabric.** Double gauze from Rico Design. White background, blue and pink splotch-like patterns, faded blue rectangular brush-like patterns. Procured by Rothery in Bordeaux, France.

Etymology: *Lorna* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

Remarks:

- In early 2020, presumably before March 2020 when the COVID-19 pandemic began to spread intensely, Rothery visited Bordeaux, France. She found a local fabric shop which had 1.5 m remaining of a double gauze fabric from Rico Design; she bought and stashed it (Rothery (2020a)).
- We note a discrepancy in Lorna’s family name in the EXIF metadata; see Section 5.1.

Specimens examined:

- Holotype.
- **Rothery E530.KL** — Photograph. United Kingdom. wb. Lorna.R., © Lorna Rothery or Lorna Malkin (name seen in EXIF data; see Section 5.1), 2020, all rights reserved.
 - **Page:** See Rothery (2020a).
 - **SHA2-256:** a48b736b7bb47f251db41d827ca4d7024fb4882889178347d65276eddb153ca5
 - **Raw image URLs**
 - * **Original:** <https://lornarothery.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/05/165d5796-3a33-4292-a302-c1f879b4e530.jpg>
 - * **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260317104650/https://lornarothery.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/05/165d5796-3a33-4292-a302-c1f879b4e530.jpg>

4.9.2 *Kewpepla lornaebis*

Kewpepla lornaebis Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Holotype: Rothery 8861KL — Photograph. 3024×3024. Exposure: 1/50s. F-stop: 1.8. Focal: 4.0 mm. Camera: iPhone 7. Lens: iPhone 7 back camera 3.99mm f/1.8. Ventral view, hair positioned ventrally and obscuring wearer’s left. *Kewpepla lornaebis* wb. Lorna.R., 2020. © Lorna Rothery, 2020, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Rothery (2020b)
- **SHA2-256:** 64f8a8b8d6b0d38129abb2259e0c1fb8667c5e1a5f4633644158636c27875947
- **Raw image URLs**
 - **Original:** https://lornarothery.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/img_8861.jpg
 - **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260318102735/https://lornarothery.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/img_8861.jpg

Description: Shallow angle V-neck. Ventral medial row of 4 buttons. **Buttons.** Wooden-like material, two thread holes, thread line vertical. Thread holes lie in circular inset. Sourced from Minerva. Bodice in UK size 8, sleeve significantly shortened, terminates roughly parallel to first button. Pleated gathered section immediately inferior to fourth button. **Fabric.** Meadow Dim in Rayon from Art Gallery Fabrics. R-46302. 76 g / m². Floral, 9 species, no known correlation to any botanical taxa. Est. 0.5 m of fabric used.

Etymology: *Lorna* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix + *-bis* “twice”, as it is the second *Kewpepla* sp. from Rothery to be described.

Remarks:

- This is Rothery’s second make of a *Kewpepla*, published with a similar title as her first make, *Kewpepla lornae*. As such, confusion may ensue.

Specimens examined: See holotype information.

4.9.3 *Kewpepla mariae*

Kewpepla mariae sp. nov.

Holotype: Marie FR.80957KM — Photograph. 1080×809. *Kewpepla mariae* laid out on table. © @la_ptite_marie3, 2018, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Marie of F. (2018)
- **SHA2-256:** 3fa353cefbc7ab862b7695a661f84bf9997064e985792f5ac99e399f003a0c48
- **Raw image URLs**
 - **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260322142053/https://instagram.fmnl35-1.fna.fbcdn.net/v/t51.82787-15/629182385_18447910603096148_441175304354280957_n.jpg?stp=dst-jpg_e35_tt6&_nc_cat=102&ig_cache_key=MTc4NDAwODIyMzIwNDk5ODIzMw%3D%3D.3-ccb7-5&ccb=7-5&_nc_sid=58cdad&efg=eyJ2ZW5jb2RlX3RhZyI6InhwaWRzLjEwODB4ODA5LnNkci5DMjY5J9&_nc_ohc=0RKgmEWatcMQ7kNvwE5d0e7&_nc_oc=AdpEiMGgGeiNlCzY2hNDE9koQSoLiioLyXsQYFTUK_wLPL6AXgY3DFIgpNy-kexEge0&_nc_ad=z-m&_nc_cid=0&_nc_zt=23&_nc_ht=instagram.fmnl35-1.fna&_nc_gid=LrBodihguAgDTJzr4G3kzA&_nc_ss=7a32e&oh=00_Afz_onYXQamv3Ej5KBfUXdksIQRjIb8afi_9BlMZ0-pjw&oe=69C5B945

Description: Lack of skirt. Two distinct regions on bodice. On superior portion, bilateral ventral dart, from third button to border of inferior portion. White thread serging across top, dorsal interior. **Fabric.** Unknown material. Maroon-like color, plain. **Buttons.** Ventral medial row of 10 buttons. Metallic shank buttons, no visible thread holes.

Etymology: *Marie* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

Specimens examined: See holotype information.

4.10 Genus *Kewthea*

Kewthea Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Diagnosis: Presence of V-shaped neckline, ventral medial button row, with sleeves covering shoulders.

4.10.1 *Kewthea chantellae*

Kewthea chantellae Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Holotype: *Chantelle 2018.03KC* — Photograph. 2268×3024. EXIF metadata stripped. *Kewthea chantellae* wb. Chantelle, 2018. Tight crop, features dress in more detail. Hair positioned ventrally, no important features obscured. Holding lateral edges of skirt apart. © Chantelle or unknown photographer, 2018, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Cleary (2018)
- **SHA2-256:** d481e016d0b805bb693d43e1fa8195b03ffd72c02cbe4d0938d7517e8fee4e57
- **Raw image URLs**
 - **Original:** <https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/2211/5041/files/chantelle3.jpg?v=1524850885>
 - **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260318171723/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/2211/5041/files/chantelle3.jpg?v=1524850885>

Description: Shallow angle V-neck. Ventral medial button row. Skirt terminates slightly superior to knee. Sleeves terminate superior to elbow. **Buttons.** Seashell-like button. Green, yellow, and cyan reflection. **Fabric.** Square fabric. Stylized yellow and red flower; two yellow leaves, red petals. Second style of flower stylized orange, gray, and red flower, with light bronze stem. No correspondence to real-world botanical taxa.

Etymology: *Chantelle* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

Remarks: The post is attributed to Harriet Cleary, but the post is written in the first-person perspective from Chantelle’s perspective.

Specimens examined:

- Holotype.
- *Chantelle 2018.02KC* — Photograph. 2268×3024. EXIF metadata stripped. Ventral view, subject looking up. Hair positioned ventrally, no important features obscured. *Kewthea chantellae* wb. Chantelle, 2018. © Chantelle or unknown photographer, 2018, all rights reserved.
 - **Page:** See Cleary (2018)
 - **SHA2-256:** 9e05b1f7611cba990c075f4f471aead5662ac39d96876e6f8712757f39b2c938
 - **Raw image URLs**
 - * **Original:** <https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/2211/5041/files/chantelle2.jpg?v=1524850863>
 - * **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260318172030/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/2211/5041/files/chantelle2.jpg?v=1524850863>
- *Chantelle 2018.04KC* — Photograph. 2238×3024. EXIF metadata stripped. Ventral view, subject looking slightly downward. Hair positioned ventrally, no important features obscured. *Kewthea chantellae* wb. Chantelle, 2018. © Chantelle or unknown photographer, 2018, all rights reserved.
 - **Page:** See Cleary (2018)
 - **SHA2-256:** ec8998c45b2c4d08ab551a801f2a148848f1ce0e3c9387ec66e8632f2819418b
 - **Raw image URLs**
 - * **Original:** <https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/2211/5041/files/chantelle4.jpg?v=1524850906>

- * **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260318171937/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/2211/5041/files/chantelle4.jpg?v=1524850906>
- **Chantelle 2018.06KC** — Photograph. 3024×4032. EXIF metadata stripped. Dress laid ventrally on table, showing buttons. © Chantelle or unknown photographer, 2018, all rights reserved.
 - **Page:** See Cleary (2018)
 - **SHA2-256:** 9af50852035cc5669b8523a0e3b197d5135284cbc551d509e3c5e3997859328a
 - **Raw image URLs**
 - * **Original:** <https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/2211/5041/files/chantelle6.jpg?v=1524850970>
 - * **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260318172049/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/2211/5041/files/chantelle6.jpg?v=1524850970>
- **Chantelle 2018.07KC** — Photograph. 3024×4032. EXIF metadata stripped. Zoomed out shot of dress laid on table. © Chantelle or unknown photographer, 2018, all rights reserved.
 - **Page:** See Cleary (2018)
 - **SHA2-256:** 1017fd78cc3f2e158b0bcf9c86f28c13a63d4599aa8311bcbbdc4948a31c3ca7
 - **Raw image URLs**
 - * **Original:** <https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/2211/5041/files/chantelle7.jpg?v=1524850993>
 - * **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260318172051/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/2211/5041/files/chantelle7.jpg?v=1524850993>

4.10.2 *Kewthea evae*

Kewthea evae Lemuria, 2026

Holotype: *Eva 2947KE* — Photograph. 900×900. EXIF metadata stripped; exposure, f-stop, lens foc. len unknown. Mirror selfie. Ventral view. *Kewthea evae* wb. *Eva*, 2019. © Kate Eva, 2019, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Eva (2018a)
- **SHA2-256:** 79d6e4321fd0295ceb7bc6434aec7596c2a4c2b83e3e7b265d704891dc8eb14f.
- **Raw image URLs**
 - **Original:** https://kateevadesigns.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/09/img_2947.jpg
 - **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260317075603/https%3A//kateevadesigns.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/09/img_2947.jpg

Description: Sleeves terminate superior to elbow. Ventral medial button row of 8 buttons. Buttons 1–3 have two holes. Thread line vertical. Buttons 4–8 have four holes. Buttons sourced from *Eva*’s vintage stash. **Fabric.** Crepe. Black background with stylized floral print. Flowers do not correspond to any known species. Floral print color roughly caramel/pale yellow. Sourced from Guthrie & Ghani.

Etymology: *Eva* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

Remarks:

- *Eva* reported fit issues, though she attributed them to her body. She wrote in *Eva* (2018a) that she learned she had broad shoulders with a smaller waist and bust, from an online course from By Hand London; and theorized that if she purchased an RTW tea dress, the body would be excessively large. As a result, when making *Kewthea evae*, she graded between sizes.

Specimens examined:

- Holotype.
- ***Eva 0120KE*** — Photograph. 1536×2048. EXIF metadata stripped; exposure, f-stop, lens foc. len unknown. Ventral view. Jacket worn over dress (unclassified). *Kewthea evae* wb. *Eva*, 2019. © Kate Eva or unknown photographer, 2019, all rights reserved.
 - **Page:** See *Eva* (2018a)
 - **SHA2-256:** 4cf40acd6dde11352f2cf0b993849f641ae94e3064991184f0f053ceaa81914b.
 - **Raw image URLs:**
 - * **Original:** https://kateevadesigns.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/10/img_0120.jpg
 - * **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260317080030/https%3A//kateevadesigns.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/10/img_0120.jpg

4.10.3 *Kewthea lornae*

Kewthea lornae Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Holotype: *Rothery 3618KL* — Photograph. 983×1748. Exposure 1/30s, f-stop 6.3, lens foc. len 18mm (35mm equiv. 33.5mm), ISO 400. Camera: Canon EOS 90D. Lens: EF-S18-55mm f/3.5-5.6 IS STM. United Kingdom. *Kewthea lornae* wb. Lorna.R., 2025. © Lorna Rothery or Lorna Malkin (name seen in EXIF data; see Section 5.1), 2025, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Rothery (2025)
- **SHA2-256:** eab2676a36834c7d23b82b731268c7a3dc0ca3dc8b33453d30990648369df092.
- **Raw image URLs**
 - **Original:** https://lornarothery.com/wp-content/uploads/2025/07/img_3618-1.jpg
 - **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260317093131/https://lornarothery.com/wp-content/uploads/2025/07/img_3618-1.jpg

Description: Sleeves terminate superior to elbow. Ventral medial button row of 14 buttons, two thread holes running horizontally. 4 buttons on bodice, 10 on skirt. Thread color varies between white and red. Fabric gathers distally on right arm (wearer’s perspective). Sewn on Janome DKS100 machine, stitch len. 2.6 mm, width 3 mm. Gutermann polyester thread, color 659 for dress; button thread unspecified cotton thread from Aurifil. **Fabric.** Meet MILK Two-Tone Check Tencel Lyocell Twill Fabric in Powder Pink. Check pattern, two subtle shades.

Etymology: *Lorna* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

Remarks:

- Cameras such as the 90D typically produce larger images than 983×1748. We do not have a 90D in our possession, but theorize that Rothery likely downscaled the original image before publication to her blog, or less likely, used a lower-quality setting in the camera. We found the usage of Adobe Lightroom 10.4.1 (iOS) in the EXIF metadata of the holotype. We observe a consistent -1 suffix in image filenames (e.g. *img_3618-1.jpg*), and 404 errors in attempting to retrieve unsuffixed versions (e.g. *img_3618.jpg*), suggesting the existence of a higher-quality image type inaccessible to us.
- We note a discrepancy in Lorna’s family name in the EXIF metadata; see Section 5.1.
- *Kewthea lornae* is perhaps the most recent specimen of *Kewthea* and of the Kew dress, showing that it still ranges to 2025. The Kewoidea (cold-shoulder Kew), while still sewable, has not seen any specimens dating to the 2020s; while the Kewthidae (tea dress) and Helikewidae (sundress), less prone to the fashion cycle, still persist today.

Specimens examined:

- Holotype.
- **Rothery 3603KL** — Photograph. 926×1218. Exposure 1/250s, f-stop 3.5, lens foc. len 18mm (35mm equiv. 33.5), ISO 500. Camera: Canon EOS 90D. Lens EF-S18-55mm f/3.5-5.6 IS STM. Dress in incomplete state, laid on table, ventral side up. © Lorna Rothery or Lorna Malkin (name seen in EXIF data; see Section 5.1), 2025, all rights reserved.
 - **Page:** See Rothery (2025)
 - **SHA2-256:** 5b0ff8b5d9ddb59d32181859adefe177e1ef99de31681e3d8fe24c1ba6d080d2
 - **Raw image URLs**
 - * **Original:** https://lornarothery.com/wp-content/uploads/2025/07/img_3603-1.jpg
 - * **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260317093137/https://lornarothery.com/wp-content/uploads/2025/07/img_3603-1.jpg
- **Rothery 3637KL** — Photograph. 1080×1920. Exposure 1/30s, f-stop 6.3, lens foc. len 18mm (35mm equiv. 33.5mm), ISO 400. Camera: Canon EOS 90D. Lens EF-S18-55mm f/3.5-5.6 IS STM. Slightly truncated ventral view. Subject smiling, facing upward. Slight motion blur on hands and inferior portions of skirt. *Kewthea lornae* wb. Lorna.R., 2025, © Lorna Rothery or Lorna Malkin (name seen in EXIF data; see Section 5.1), 2025, all rights reserved.
 - **Page:** See Rothery (2025)
 - **SHA2-256:** 3def2839e8e0686b451d3fd216290a69fc8b5cf567dff45da71b5444908ad77d
 - **Raw image URLs**
 - * **Original:** https://lornarothery.com/wp-content/uploads/2025/07/img_3637-1.jpg

- * **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260317093300/https://lornarothery.com/wp-content/uploads/2025/07/img_3637-1.jpg

4.10.4 *Kewthea lornoblae*

Kewthea lornoblae Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Holotype: *Rothery 6377KL* — Photograph. 1200×1600. EXIF metadata stripped. *Kewthea lornoblae* wb. Lorna.R., 2020. Ventral view, full body, subject smiling, hair positioned ventrally. Closer to subject, subject facing slightly to her right. © Lorna Rothery, 2020, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Rothery (2020c).
- **SHA2-256:** 36cd6fa2214d996b69b14b0e49ad8a7a4b0216a6666f9f461a18263293cd7d96
- **Raw image URLs**
 - **Original:** <https://lornarothery.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/e88a93f9-3466-4082-b898-aa11e637ef7a.jpg>
 - **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260319183540/https://lornarothery.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/e88a93f9-3466-4082-b898-aa11e637ef7a.jpg>

Description: Sleeves ruched, terminating superior to elbow. Skirt terminates at knee. Numerous clumps of fabric along hem. **Buttons.** Ventral medial button row, 9 buttons. 3 on bodice, 6 on skirt. Spacing unequal between second and third button. Top three buttonholes sewn by machine. Rest of buttonholes hand-sewn due to machine malfunction. **Fabric.** Viscose, from Fabricate. Navy-blue background, stylized flowers, most second common color by surface area teal.

Etymology: Blend of *Lorna* + *skoroblae*, corrupted form of Greek σκούρο μπλε (*skouíro ble*, “dark blue, navy blue”).

Specimens examined:

- Holotype.
- **Rothery 2234KL** — Photograph. 1200×1600. EXIF metadata stripped. *Kewthea lornoblae* wb. Lorna.R., 2020. Ventral view, full body, subject smiling, hair positioned ventrally. © Lorna Rothery, 2020, all rights reserved.
 - **Page:** See Rothery (2020c).
 - **SHA2-256:** 587495621ba7f44e3c1788d6649f88869bce261781b0d9cea28769c9cca17c1c
 - **Raw image URLs**
 - * **Original:** <https://lornarothery.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/01cd536c-1ac9-4dfb-8a53-a3c0e2234f5f.jpg>
 - * **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260319183543/https://lornarothery.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/01cd536c-1ac9-4dfb-8a53-a3c0e2234f5f.jpg>
- **Rothery 0402KL** — Photograph. 827×1446. EXIF metadata stripped. Ventral view, subject sitting on floor, looking down. *Kewthea lornoblae* wb. Lorna.R., 2020. © Lorna Rothery, 2020, all rights reserved.
 - **Page:** See Rothery (2020c).
 - **SHA2-256:** 7b5312096ac8833f362fd0e2f3b2595816a98059dd5cd0e43d4ccc92d423783b
 - **Raw image URLs**
 - * **Original:** <https://lornarothery.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/image.jpg>
 - * **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260319184423/https://lornarothery.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/image.jpg>

4.10.5 *Kewthea luscinia*

Kewthea luscinia Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Holotype: *Procter 0005KL* — Photograph. 1365×2048. EXIF metadata stripped; exposure, f-stop, lens foc. len unknown. United Kingdom. Ventral view. *Kewthea luscinia* wb. Ruth.Pr., 2019. © Ruth Procter, 2019, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Procter (2019)
- **SHA2-256:** 89aa8f34f0e84ad09bb11d3893802b1cd300eb0cdb6b67fac5e5ad99d98bc175.
- **Raw image URLs**

- **Original:** https://blogger.googleusercontent.com/img/b/R29vZ2xl/AVvXsEjTFuBwQrb4iHrqyA3EjhD2oW-6dgTD8dzk-lf6iBe3Qj4LF13kOdR0upk68Tx72jI5l8S9gMVKewmD8M8zUYx3T5YE6Zorj6jSLSYtgwrmR2D8ONDK2JgUdDRpCvQcH7_ob5RizD5hqig/s0/Nina-Lee-Kew-Dress-Sewing-Pattern-Expansion-Pack-5.JPG=s0?imgmax=0
- **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260316200715/https://blogger.googleusercontent.com/img/b/R29vZ2xl/AVvXsEjTFuBwQrb4iHrqyA3EjhD2oW-6dgTD8dzk-lf6iBe3Qj4LF13kOdR0upk68Tx72jI5l8S9gMVKewmD8M8zUYx3T5YE6Zorj6jSLSYtgwrmR2D8ONDK2JgUdDRpCvQcH7_ob5RizD5hqig/s0/Nina-Lee-Kew-Dress-Sewing-Pattern-Expansion-Pack-5.JPG=s0?imgmax=0

Description: Sleeves terminate superior to elbow. Ventral medial button row of 15 buttons, rainbow pattern, two button holes. 5 buttons on bodice, 10 on skirt. Row pattern pink, red, orange, yellow, green, cyan. Row pattern terminates at orange at most inferior button. Bilateral pockets in skirt, estimated volume equivalent to approx. one human hand and distal part of lower arm up to medial area. **Fabric.** Spotted chambray from Minerva Crafts, cotton. Dot size half of each button. Dark blue background with white polka dot background.

Etymology: *luscinia* is derived from the biological genus *Luscinia* T. Forster, 1817, the nightingale. The name *luscinia* was chosen because of the blog's title, *Nightingale & Dolittle*. The blog itself was named *Nightingale & Dolittle* after two girls in Procter's extended family named Florence and Eliza were born; ultimately in reference to both Florence Nightingale and Eliza Doolittle. *Dolittle*, in reference to the blog, is not a typo.

Specimens examined: See holotype information.

4.10.6 *Kewthea modistaflora*

Kewthea modistaflora sp. nov.

Holotype: *Modista 9861KM* — Photograph. 3024×4032. Exposure: 1/17s. F-stop: 9. Focal: 4.0 mm. Lens: iPhone 7 back camera 3.99mm f/1.8. Camera: iPhone 7. Ventral view, hair positioned laterally. Image ends superior to hemline. *Kewthea modistaflora* wb. Sally of M., 2020. © Sally (Modista Sewing), 2020, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** Sally of M. (2020)
- **SHA2-256:** 489458a350641f3a0863d78f2b5e7681ce717ec189f7d4b1287b727a2ecae087
- **Raw image URLs**
 - **Original:** https://modistasewing.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/img_9861.jpg
 - **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260317232455/https://modistasewing.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/img_9861.jpg

Description: Sleeves terminate superior to elbow. V-neck. Skirt terminates slightly inferior to knee. Five buttons, three on bodice, two on skirt. Curved square, two thread holes, mixed rotation. On right sleeve (wearer's perspective), pattern discontinuity at downward angle. **Fabric.** Viscose. White background, floral print, no known correlation to any known botanical species.

Etymology: *Modista*, name of the blog, + *flora* “flower”.

Specimens examined:

- Holotype.
- **Modista 9929KM** — Photograph. 3024×4032. Exposure: 1/2907s. F-stop: 1.8. Focal: 4.0 mm. Lens: iPhone 7 back camera 3.99mm f/1.8. Camera: iPhone 7. Ventral view. Subject facing forward, head slightly leaning right. Denim jacket (unclassified) worn above dress, tied together at inferior end. *Kewthea modistaflora* wb. Sally of M., 2020. © Unknown photographer on behalf of Sally (Modista Sewing), 2020, all rights reserved.
 - **Page:** See Sally of M. (2020)
 - **SHA2-256:** d4fcc57a8ab9e9c8f622228e2ce919ed9a08a0aab70940d774f96778ef825df7
 - **Raw image URLs**
 - * **Original:** https://modistasewing.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/img_9929.jpg
 - * **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260317233258/https://modistasewing.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/img_9929.jpg
- **Modista 9943KM** — Photograph. 2638×3515. Exposure: 1/1277s. F-stop: 1.8. Focal: 4.0 mm. Lens: iPhone 7 back camera 3.99mm f/1.8. Camera: iPhone 7. Ventral view. Subject looking to her left. Phone held by

unknown photographer in reflection. Denim jacket (unclassified) worn above dress, tied together at inferior end. *Kewthea modistaflorea* wb. Sally of M., 2020. © Unknown photographer on behalf of Sally (Modista Sewing), 2020, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Sally of M. (2020)
- **SHA2-256:** ee0802a12a5f88486ba72d2a9a685eb35e3080dfa6f1bd1474693ebe0e33b231
- **Raw image URLs**
 - * **Original:** https://modistasewing.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/img_9943.jpg
 - * **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260317233256/https://modistasewing.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/img_9943.jpg

4.11 Genus *Kewthicata*

Kewthicata gen. nov.

Diagnosis: *Kewthicata* is distinguished by the presence of gathering on the superior area of the skirt, immediately inferior to the bodice–skirt transition.

4.11.1 *Kewthicata juliae*

Kewthicata juliae sp. nov.

Holotype: *Julie 2018.28918KJ* — Photograph. 1080×1350. EXIF metadata stripped. Zoomed out ventral view. Subject at ease. Multiple buttons unfastened. *Kewthicata juliae* wb. Julie of the W.M., 2018. © Julie (@julielovestosew), 2018, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Julie of the W.M. (2018).
- **SHA2-256:** 5e210bb4de5c05338465e8ca884fa57bbfccb2badfc584e14f430b0192ce098
- **Raw image URLs:**
 - **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260321151521/https://instagram.fmnl35-1.fna.fbcdn.net/v/t51.82787-15/622827767_18343980316233138_7161215710540728918_n.jpg?stp=dst-jpg_e35_tt6&_nc_cat=111&ig_cache_key=MTgyMzUyMTU1NDM3ODk2NjYxMw%3D%3D.3-ccb7-5&ccb=7-5&_nc_sid=58cdad&efg=eyJ2ZW5jb2RlX3RhZyI6InhwaWRzLjEwODB4MTM1MC5zZHIuQzMifQ%3D%3D&_nc_ohc=6eiudw8PanYQ7kNvwFUn9vZ&_nc_oc=Adr9s9lSjUSUaxhuJ4aOoM2_0wqtX5UaSOuwja6FYZLWHT36vbH3a5dnFcLS3-y-m6c&_nc_ad=z-m&_nc_cid=0&_nc_zt=23&_nc_ht=instagram.fmnl35-1.fna&_nc_gid=T6i1d0NsFhWF10BVvhLqHA&_nc_ss=7a30f&oh=00_AfzOMwulSGsnROshWqlyEUzqjBE3cjDQopcQaEPdh8oizw&oe=69C47E5B

Description: Sleeves terminate superior to elbow at distal upper arm. Shallow angle V neck. Skirt terminates slightly superior to knee, with gathering at bodice–skirt transition. **Buttons.** Ventral medial button row, 16 buttonholes. Buttons circular, two thread holes, thread line horizontal. Numerous buttons unfastened in holotype. **Fabric.** Black/dark background. Orange, pale orange, and caramel-colored print on fabric, low density. Unknown material.

Etymology: *Julia* + *-ae*, feminine genitive suffix.

Specimens examined: See holotype information.

4.12 Genus *Trunkewia*

Trunkewia Lemuria, 2026

Diagnosis: Distinguished from other members of Helikewidae by the lack of a skirt.

4.12.1 *Trunkewia ninae*

Trunkewia ninae Lemuria, 2026; first public desc.

Holotype: *Nina 0296TN* — Photograph. 2668×3707. EXIF metadata stripped; exposure, f-stop, lens foc. len unknown. United Kingdom, London. Zoomed-out view. Right strap (wearer’s perspective) slightly obscured by ventrally positioned hair. *Trunkewia ninae* wb. Nina, 2018. © Nina Chang-Smith or unknown photographer, 2018, all rights reserved.

- **Page:** See Chang-Smith (2018).

- **SHA2-256:** a8962c67667a028febbd6b9bbfa1a6af25f3296a2fbf430f7cde3a5ecbb56a22.
- **Raw image URLs**
 - **Original:** https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0725/7833/5029/files/IMG_0296-1.jpg
 - **IA:** https://web.archive.org/web/20260316191704/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0725/7833/5029/files/IMG_0296-1.jpg

Description: Ventral medial row of 5 buttons. Terminates at transpyloric plane. Shallow angle V-neck. Bilateral ventral lateral darts extend until parallel to third button. **Fabric.** Plain white.

Etymology: *Nina* + *-ae*, feminine genitive form.

Specimens examined: See holotype information.

4.13 Genus *Trunkewia* subg. *Illecebrosus*

Trunkewia subgenus *Illecebrosus* subg. nov.

All three species in *T.* subg. *Illecebrosus* are defined by the holotype *Roseberry Trunkewia-1*, a three-image collage assembled by Nina Lee for Chang-Smith (2018), and the only surviving evidence of *T.* subg. *Illecebrosus* due to the deletion of @epp.roseberry.couture’s account.

Diagnosis: Having been sewn by Stéphanie.T.

Etymology: From the species *Rubus illecebrosus* Focke 1899, known in Japan as バライチゴ, literally “roseberry”. It was the first result when searching for “roseberry”. Roseberry is in turn, taken from the wearer’s Instagram handle.

Holotype: *Roseberry Trunkewia-1* — Photograph, collage. 3711×1194. EXIF metadata stripped; collage format not amenable to per-image metadata. *T. rosacrania*, *rubera*, and *viridis* wb. Stéphanie.T.

- **Page:** See Chang-Smith (2018).
- **SHA2-256:** 7f90faa8a161da4b1dea5b9c6c1262e6e5c2008dc2ac4384bb42723f7c8b262a
- **Raw image URLs:**
 - **Original:** <https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0725/7833/5029/files/Kew-tops.jpg>
 - **IA:** <https://web.archive.org/web/20260321015534/https://cdn.shopify.com/s/files/1/0725/7833/5029/files/Kew-tops.jpg>

Type species (for subgenus): *Trunkewia rosacrania*.

4.13.1 *Trunkewia rosacrania*

Trunkewia rosacrania sp. nov.

Holotype: *Roseberry Trunkewia-1*, left panel.

Etymology: Latin *rosa* “rose” + *crania*, pseudo-Latin feminine form of *cranium* “skull”, from the features on the fabric.

Description: Shallow angle V-neck. Bilateral single straps. Ventral medial button row of eight buttons. Bodice terminates between navel and pelvic area. **Fabric.** Black background, stylized skulls in a variety of facial expressions, multiple roses with full leaves (*Rosa* L.). Unknown material.

4.13.2 *Trunkewia rubera*

Trunkewia rubera sp. nov.

Holotype: *Roseberry Trunkewia-1*, center panel.

Etymology: Latin *ruber* “red”.

Description: Shallow angle V-neck. Bilateral single straps. Ventral medial button row of five buttons. Bodice tied together medially at inferior end, and terminates superior to navel. **Fabric.** White background, vaguely floral pattern, red. Unknown material.

4.13.3 *Trunkewia viridis*

Trunkewia viridis sp. nov.

Holotype: Roseberry Trunkewia-1, right panel.

Etymology: Latin *viridis* “green”.

Description: Shallow angle V-neck. Bilateral single straps. Ventral medial button row of ~7 buttons. Bodice terminates between navel and superior to pelvic area. **Fabric.** Vaguely off-white background with multiple light green and dark blue/indigo patterns. Unknown material.

5 General remarks

5.1 Lorna Rothery

While examining the EXIF metadata of Rothery’s images, we discovered the name *Lorna Malkin*. We have no information on this name.

Lorna’s two *Kewpepla* makes had the same blog post titles; we were uncertain as to which was *Kewpepla lornae* and which was *Kewpepla lornaebis*. Given that *-bis* means “twice”, we decided to name the tops in the May and June 2020 posts *lornae* and *lornaebis* respectively, based on chronological order.

5.2 Type specimen naming

We also find it important to develop naming conventions for type specimen photographs. So far, we have settled on a convention of a single name for the wearer (either given or family), followed by either an alphanumeric identifier or numeric identifier, with the initials of the species in question suffixed for more disambiguation.

5.3 Per-site archival considerations

Certain websites presented issues during archival; for example, WordPress.com blogs and Meta CDN URLs.

Meta’s CDN generates temporary image URLs and appears to serve different-sized versions at random depending on the user and browser; furthermore, URL signing and expiry worsens this problem. However, the Internet Archive is capable of ingesting these temporary URLs, meaning that while the original Meta URL will rot, immediately submitting it to Save Page Now will trigger archival.

Many blogs hosted on WordPress.com tend to serve HTML previews of images, despite URLs ending in .jpg or other image file formats. How WordPress.com chooses to serve either raw images or HTML page previews is unpredictable. Content negotiation, while possible, compli-

cates archival. However, the Archive Team has crawlers capable of retrieving the content properly; we thus use WARC’s generated by their crawlers as a fallback for when Wayback Machine capture fails.

5.4 Long-term name disambiguation

On the Internet, and especially the sewing community we document in detail, it is common to only be known mononymically, such as by a first name. The author, Lemuria himself is an example; though “Lemuria” is not his legal given name. The large number of sewists online mean that statistically, collisions are very likely; as an example, the three species *Kewisia sarae*, *Kewabotonia sarae*, and *Helikewisia sarae* were all worn by entirely different people named Sarah.

Often, sewists’ last names can be identified through OSINT work, but this has privacy implications, especially when these names are disseminated in a system meant for long-term archival such as the taxonomy and the *Journal*. As such, in place of last names, the LCT-01 has started assigning locational disambiguators to people, based on their locations or their blogs; for example, the sewist Sarah, from Brooklyn, and known on Instagram as @sarahssewingchronicles, has the LCT-01 person abbreviation *Sarah’s S.C.*

But in cases where even a general location or other identifier (e.g. blog name, internal filename) is unavailable, such as Maria and her *Helikewisia mariae*, whose sole holotype has the filename `Maria-Nina-Lee-Kew-Dress-Expansion-16-28-scaled.jpg` on `ninalee.co.uk`’s CDN, locational disambiguators are nearly impossible to assign.

For these cases, a numerical identifier system based on comet naming may be most suitable. Lemuria has long used a system of numeric identifiers (the “Unnamable Humanoids Center”¹⁵ ID) based on comet naming to assign provisional names to people whose true names are unknown.

¹⁵The name is a misnomer; “humanoid” was selected during its creation as Lemuria believed it sounded “smarter”. Additionally, non-human animals such as cats have UHC IDs in Lemuria’s systems.

6 Identification key

To determine the genus in which a Kew dress is placed:

- 01 Shoulders exposed: 02; Shoulders covered: family Kewthidae (03).
- 02 Sleeves lateral to upper arm: superfamily Kewoidea (04). No sleeves: family Helikewidae (05).
- 03 Garment has skirt or no bottom: subfamily Kewthinae (06). Garment has Portobello trousers: subfamily Kewbellinae.
- 04 Ventral medial button row (VMBR) present: family Kewidae (08). VMBR absent: family Plesikewidae (09).
- 05 Garment has bottom: tribe Helikewinae (17). Garment lacks bottom: tribe Trunkewinae (18).
- 06 Garment has skirt: Tribe Kewthini (07). Garment has no skirt: Genus *Kewpepla*.
- 07 Garment has gathering at superior end of skirt: Genus *Kewthicata* (26). Otherwise, genus *Kewthea* (27).
- 08 Straight skirt (same as default skirt in Chang-Smith (2017a)): genus *Kewisia* (10). Gathering at superior end: genus *Kewplicata* (11). Slight parabolic shape before shallow inward angle (as seen on the rightmost skirt of Chang-Smith (n.d.)): genus *Kewparabola* (12).
- 09 Dress has skirt: Subfamily Plesikewinae (13). Dress has trousers: Subfamily Kewasalinae (14).
- 10, 11, 12 End.
- 13 Neckline of sleeve and bodice at different levels: genus *Florankewia* (15). Parallel levels, or descent from Jen Walker's hack: genus *Kewabotonia* (16).
- 14 Trousers not originating from Portobello: genus *Kewasalia*. Trousers are that of Portobello: possible subgenus of *Kewasalia*. End.
- 15, 16 End.
- 17 Garment bottom similar in appearance to Kewbello: *Helikewbellini* (19). Garment has skirt: tribe Helikewini (20).
- 18 Genus *Trunkewia*. End.
- 19 Genus *Helikewbellia*. End.
- 20 Ventral medial button row present: 21. Ventral medial button row absent: genus *Helikewabotonia* (25).
- 21 Straight skirt (same as default skirt in Chang-Smith (2017a)): genus *Helikewisia* (22). Gathering at superior end: genus *Helikewplicata* (23). Slight parabolic shape before shallow inward angle (as seen on the rightmost skirt of Chang-Smith (n.d.)): genus *Helikewparabola* (24).
- 22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27 End.

7 Appendix

7.1 Person abbreviations

In this paper, we used the following person abbreviations.

- **Alice.Ir.** — Alice Irvine (<https://aliceirvine.com/>; Instagram: [@its.alice.irvine](#))
- **Alice.W.** — Alice Wang (Instagram: [@alice_x_wang](#)), author of the blog *Queen of Darts*.
- **Bernice** — Bernice (Instagram: [@sewbee73](#)), a sewist based in the San Francisco Bay Area.
- **Eleanor S.** — Eleanor (Instagram: [@eleanor_sews](#)). Abbreviation stands for *Eleanor Sews*.¹⁶
- **Elsa of L.** — Elsa, author of the blog *La Casa Cactus*. Abbreviation stands for *Elsa of La Casa Cactus*.
- **Emily of L.** — Emily (Instagram: [@selfassemblyrequired](#)), author of the blog *Self Assembly Required*. Abbreviation stands for *Emily of London*.
- **Emma of N.** — Emma (Instagram: [@craftyclyde](#)), author of the blog *Crafty Clyde*. Abbreviation stands for *Emma of Norfolk*.
- **Erin.M.** — Erin Madalone (Instagram: [@poeticmemorysewing](#)), an American sewist based in New Jersey.
- **Eva** — Kate Eva.
- **Gingerthread** — Gingerthread Girl (Jen Walker; Instagram: [@gingerthreadgirl](#)).
- **Joy of B.** — Joy (Instagram: [@sew.with.joy](#)), a sewist based in Brooklyn. Abbreviation stands for *Joy of Brooklyn*.
- **Julie of the W.M.** — Julie (Instagram: [@julielovestosew](#)). Abbreviation stands for *Julie of the West Midlands*.
- **Lehrer** — Kristin Lehrer (Instagram: [@voolenvine](#)), known online as Voolenvine. Operator of Voolenvine Yarns (<https://voolenvineyarns.com>).

¹⁶If a surname or second name being treated as a surname is being abbreviated to form a person abbreviation, a dot is placed between the first name and the initial. If a verb, noun, or other word from the person's handle or alias is being abbreviated, a regular space is used instead.

- **Lemuria** — Lemuria (<https://lemuria.ph>), Filipino programmer and independent clothing taxonomist; author of *Lemuria's (Informal) Journal of Clothing Taxonomy* (<https://lct01.lemuria.ph>).
- **Liz of G.** — Liz, author of the blog *Girl Can Sew*. Abbreviation stands for *Liz of Girl Can Sew*.
- **Lorna.R.** — Lorna Rothery (<https://lornarothery.com/>), the most prolific sewist among the Kewthidae, with four documented specimens.
- **Marie.K.** — Marie Koupparis (Instagram: [@stitchodyyssey](#)), author of the blog *A Stitching Odyssey*.
- **Nina** — Nina Chang-Smith (Instagram: [@ninaleeloves](#)). Operator of Nina Lee Patterns (<https://ninalee.co.uk>).
- **Parker** — Fiona Parker (Instagram: [@fionaparker17](#)), British sewist, author of the blog *Diary of a Chain Stitcher* (<https://chainstitcher.blogspot.com/>).
- **Rachael** — Rachael Beaumont (Instagram: [@sew_prettyful](#)), author of the blog *Sew Prettyful*.
- **Ruth.Pr.** — Ruth Procter, author of the blog *Nightingale & Dolittle*.
- **Sally of M.** — Sally, author of the blog *Modista Sewing*. Abbreviation stands for *Sally of Modista*.
- **Sarah of T.** — Sarah (Instagram: [@craftily_handmade](#)), author of the blog *Craftily Handmade*. Abbreviation stands for *Sarah of Tasmania*.
- **Sarah.D.** — Sarah Donnison (Instagram: [@sewsarahstitch](#)), the *Sewist Organiser*¹⁷
- **Sarah's S.C.** — Sarah (Instagram: [@sarahssewingchronicles](#)), a Minerva ambassador. Abbreviation stands for *Sarah's Sewing Chronicles*.
- **Stéphanie.T.** — Stéphanie Terranova / Terranova Stéphanie. Order of name elements unknown.
- **Vic.B.** — Vic Broad (Instagram: [@sewvee](#)), author of the blog *Sewvee*.

7.1.1 Botanical abbreviations

These botanical abbreviations were used:

- **Cronquist** — Cronquist
- **Juss.** — Antoine Laurent de Jussieu
- **L.** — Carl Linnaeus
- **Lam.** — Jean-Baptiste Lamarck
- **Leichtlin** — Max Leichtlin
- **Takht** — Armen Takhtajan
- **Thunb.** — Carl Peter Thunberg
- **W.Zimm.** — Walter Max Zimmermann

7.2 Image specimen list

We present a list of the image specimen identifiers we have assigned in this paper for ease of reference or future database creation.

- *Alice 18651KR*
- *Alice 27962KR*
- *Alice 29682KR*
- *Alice 33300KR*
- *Alice 88719KR*
- *Alice 94531KR*
- *Bernice 37957KB*
- *Bernice 48621KB*
- *Cecilia 849728HC*
- *Chantelle 2018.02KC*
- *Chantelle 2018.03KC*
- *Chantelle 2018.04KC*
- *Chantelle 2018.06KC*
- *Chantelle 2018.07KC*
- *Eleanor 2018.64378KE*
- *Elsa 2021.0013KE*
- *Emily 3668HA*
- *Emily 3670HA*
- *Emma 2019-001.HA*
- *Emma 2019-001.HS*
- *Emma K01.HQ*
- *Eva 0098FV*
- *Eva 0120KE*
- *Eva 2947KE*
- *Eva 3222FV*
- *Eva 3318KE*
- *Eva 4be-FL*
- *Eva 4be-FL*
- *Genya 2023.0004KG*
- *Gingerthread 0212KZ*
- *Irvine 0001HI*
- *Joy 112.26042HL*
- *Joy 112.69087HL*
- *Julie 2018.28918KJ*
- *Lehrer 0001.G65Z*
- *Lehrer 2018.12320KK*
- *Lehrer 2018.22063HKEW*
- *Lehrer 2018.23250KK*

¹⁷The *Journal* uses Philippine English, which is based on American English. We preserve the original spelling of the rank here.

- *Lehrer* 2018.25504KK
- *Lehrer* 2018.43603HKEW
- *Lehrer* 2018.46021KK
- *Lehrer* 2018.73568KK
- *Lehrer* 2018.86738HKEW
- *Lehrer* 2018.88823HKEW
- *Lehrer* 2018.94528HKEW
- *Liz* GCS2018.001KL
- *Liz* GCS2018.002KL
- *Liz* GCS2018.003KL
- *Liz* GCS2018.004KL
- *Madalone* 4823HE
- *Madalone Inst-1HE*
- *Maria* 0001HM
- *Marie* 2451a-KM
- *Marie* 2456a-KM
- *Marie* 2468a-KM
- *Marie* 2470a-KM
- *Marie* 2485KM
- *Marie* 2494KM
- *Marie* FR.80957KM
- *Modista* 9861KM
- *Modista* 9929KM
- *Modista* 9943KM
- *Nina* 0001HN
- *Nina* 0296TN
- *Parker* 0001KF
- *Pimsy* 0001KP
- *Procter* 0005KL
- *Rachael* 0063
- *Rachael* 0412
- *Rachael* 2018.KL05
- *Rachael* 2018.KL08
- *Rachael* 2018.KL10
- *Rachael* 2018.KL11
- *Rachael* 2018.KL13
- *Rachael* 2018.KL15
- *Rachael* 2018.KL16
- *Rachael* 2018.KL17
- *Rachael* 2018.KL19
- *Rachael* 2018.KL20
- *Roseberry Trunkewia-1*
- *Rothery* 0402KL
- *Rothery* 2234KL
- *Rothery* 3603KL
- *Rothery* 3618KL
- *Rothery* 3637KL
- *Rothery* 613D.KL
- *Rothery* 6377KL
- *Rothery* 8861KL
- *Rothery* E530.KL
- *Sally* M40C8B-KR
- *Sally* M8644KR
- *Sarah* 0082HS.AU-TAS
- *Sarah* 0085HS.AU-TAS
- *Sarah* 0087HS.AU-TAS
- *Sarah* 0088HS.AU-TAS
- *Sarah* D-2019.44536KS
- *Sarah* SC.12274KS
- *Vic* 91147KL
- *Yarngasm* 281 (V)

7.3 Acknowledgements

We used R; specifically, `ggtree`, to generate Figure 1. For information on `ggtree`, see Yu, Smith, Zhu, Guan, and Lam (2017).

We thank Nina Lee for her amazing patterns that help bolster a culture of home sewing and advance the slow fashion movement. We thank all the sewists and the sources we have cited for documenting their projects in intricate detail.

We thank the people of the Archive Team (https://wiki.archiveteam.org/wiki/Main_Page) for assistance in archiving many of the websites we visited, especially the WordPress blogs whose images the Wayback Machine could not save due to improper content negotiation.

We thank the people of the Coffee Shop on 4d2.org, where our lead author has posted fragments of the paper time and time again, for being absolutely wonderful people, and being an extra set of eyes to keep errors shallow under Linus's law; and we thank Sarah, the operator of 4d2, for fostering such a wonderful space.

7.4 Information

Lemuria's (Informal) Journal of Clothing Taxonomy is the gray literature journal of the First Lemurian Clothing Taxonomy, a system by Lemuria to assign Latin names to dresses using biological methods. The author, known mononymically as just Lemuria, is a Filipino programmer and gray literature researcher.

Disclaimer: *Lemuria's (Informal) Journal of Clothing Taxonomy* is a non-peer-reviewed, single-author, citizen science/gray literature publication with no institutional backing.

Publisher article ID: lict2026.0005 (intranet: L78.1098/lict2026.0005, not for external use)

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.19242200](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19242200) (provided by Zenodo)

At publication, the journal did not have a DOI prefix.

Work began on the paper on 2026-03-14. Descriptions were completed and proofreading began on 2026-03-23. Proofreading was completed on 2026-03-24 and published the same day.

Visit us at: <https://lct01.lemuria.ph>

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7.5 yt-dlp provenance for *Kewisia kristinae*

```
$ yt-dlp --version
2026.03.13.083652
$ yt-dlp --write-info-json --write-description 'https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=C_cpG65ZGyE'
[youtube] Extracting URL: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=C_cpG65ZGyE
[youtube] C_cpG65ZGyE: Downloading webpage
WARNING: [youtube] No supported JavaScript runtime could be found.
Only deno is enabled by default; to use another runtime add
--js-runtimes RUNTIME[:PATH] to your command/config. YouTube
extraction without a JS runtime has been deprecated, and some
formats may be missing. See https://github.com/yt-dlp/yt-dlp/wiki/EJS
for details on installing one
[youtube] C_cpG65ZGyE: Downloading android vr player API JSON
[info] C_cpG65ZGyE: Downloading 1 format(s): 137+251
[info] Writing video description to:
  VoolenvVLOG : The Seamstress Tag! [C_cpG65ZGyE].description
[info] Writing video metadata as JSON to:
  VoolenvVLOG : The Seamstress Tag! [C_cpG65ZGyE].info.json
[download] Destination: VoolenvVLOG : The Seamstress Tag! [C_cpG65ZGyE].f137.mp4
[download] 100% of 115.81MiB in 00:00:23 at 5.03MiB/s
[download] Destination: VoolenvVLOG : The Seamstress Tag! [C_cpG65ZGyE].f251.webm
[download] 100% of 12.28MiB in 00:00:02 at 5.49MiB/s
[Merger] Merging formats into
  "VoolenvVLOG : The Seamstress Tag! [C_cpG65ZGyE].mkv"
Deleting original file VoolenvVLOG : The Seamstress Tag! [C_cpG65ZGyE].f137.mp4 (pass -k to keep)
Deleting original file VoolenvVLOG : The Seamstress Tag! [C_cpG65ZGyE].f251.webm (pass -k to keep)
$ sha256sum VoolenvVLOG : \ The\ Seamstress\ Tag\! \ [C_cpG65ZGyE\].mkv
26d8f585d3f683bd21a158954da41103b163bb99b88c6e1cb508bf292d9076be
VoolenvVLOG : The Seamstress Tag! [C_cpG65ZGyE].mkv
```

Terminal output has been manually newlined for ease of printing.

```
$ yt-dlp --write-info-json --write-description \
  https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=adTrJzjOXbc \
  https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BicN7eyA2U4 \
  https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=066xjOf4DhM
[youtube] Extracting URL: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=adTrJzjOXbc
[youtube] adTrJzjOXbc: Downloading webpage
WARNING: [youtube] No supported JavaScript runtime could be found.
Only deno is enabled by default; to use another runtime add
--js-runtimes RUNTIME[:PATH] to your command/config. YouTube
extraction without a JS runtime has been deprecated, and some
formats may be missing. See https://github.com/yt-dlp/yt-dlp/wiki/EJS
```

for details on installing one

[youtube] adTrJzjOXbc: Downloading android vr player API JSON

[info] adTrJzjOXbc: Downloading 1 format(s): 135+251

[info] Writing video description to:

YARNGASM: Episode 273 - "I Say Tomato, You Say ..." [adTrJzjOXbc].description

[info] Writing video metadata as JSON to:

YARNGASM: Episode 273 - "I Say Tomato, You Say ..." [adTrJzjOXbc].info.json

[download] Destination:

YARNGASM: Episode 273 - "I Say Tomato, You Say ..." [adTrJzjOXbc].f135.mp4

[download] 100% of 98.67MiB in 00:00:22 at 4.47MiB/s

[download] Destination:

YARNGASM: Episode 273 - "I Say Tomato, You Say ..." [adTrJzjOXbc].f251.webm

[download] 100% of 30.10MiB in 00:00:05 at 5.58MiB/s

[Merger] Merging formats into "YARNGASM: Episode 273 - "I Say Tomato, You Say ..." [adTrJzjOXbc].mkv"

Deleting original file

YARNGASM: Episode 273 - "I Say Tomato, You Say ..." [adTrJzjOXbc].f135.mp4

(pass -k to keep)

Deleting original file

YARNGASM: Episode 273 - "I Say Tomato, You Say ..." [adTrJzjOXbc].f251.webm

(pass -k to keep)

[youtube] Extracting URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BicN7eyA2U4>

[youtube] BicN7eyA2U4: Downloading webpage

WARNING: [youtube] No supported JavaScript runtime could be found.

Only deno is enabled by default; to use another runtime add

--js-runtimes RUNTIME[:PATH] to your command/config. YouTube

extraction without a JS runtime has been deprecated, and some

formats may be missing. See <https://github.com/yt-dlp/yt-dlp/wiki/EJS>

for details on installing one

[youtube] BicN7eyA2U4: Downloading android vr player API JSON

[info] BicN7eyA2U4: Downloading 1 format(s): 135+251

[info] Writing video description to:

YARNGASM: Episode 278 - "Living On the Edge" [BicN7eyA2U4].description

[info] Writing video metadata as JSON to:

YARNGASM: Episode 278 - "Living On the Edge" [BicN7eyA2U4].info.json

[download] Destination:

YARNGASM: Episode 278 - "Living On the Edge" [BicN7eyA2U4].f135.mp4

[download] 100% of 126.58MiB in 00:00:59 at 2.12MiB/s

[download] Destination:

YARNGASM: Episode 278 - "Living On the Edge" [BicN7eyA2U4].f251.webm

[download] 100% of 32.26MiB in 00:00:11 at 2.88MiB/s

[Merger] Merging formats into "YARNGASM: Episode 278 - "Living On the Edge" [BicN7eyA2U4].mkv"

Deleting original file

YARNGASM: Episode 278 - "Living On the Edge" [BicN7eyA2U4].f251.webm

(pass -k to keep)

Deleting original file

YARNGASM: Episode 278 - "Living On the Edge" [BicN7eyA2U4].f135.mp4

(pass -k to keep)

[youtube] Extracting URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=066xj0f4DhM>

[youtube] 066xj0f4DhM: Downloading webpage

WARNING: [youtube] No supported JavaScript runtime could be found.

Only deno is enabled by default; to use another runtime add

--js-runtimes RUNTIME[:PATH] to your command/config. YouTube

extraction without a JS runtime has been deprecated, and some

formats may be missing. See <https://github.com/yt-dlp/yt-dlp/wiki/EJS>

for details on installing one

```
[youtube] 066xjOf4DhM: Downloading android vr player API JSON
[info] 066xjOf4DhM: Downloading 1 format(s): 135+251
[info] Writing video description to:
  YARNGASM: Episode 281 - "There's Been Spinning" [066xjOf4DhM].description
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  YARNGASM: Episode 281 - "There's Been Spinning" [066xjOf4DhM].info.json
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Deleting original file
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  (pass -k to keep)
Deleting original file
  YARNGASM: Episode 281 - "There's Been Spinning" [066xjOf4DhM].f135.mp4
  (pass -k to keep)

0914ac6be8ed66acb413a553157cc57d8b8286a5173818045f2e643ec65e290c
YARNGASM: Episode 273 - "I Say Tomato, You Say ..." [adTrJzjOXbc].mkv

496d067484a1f313eab59b28faef186cda44e3b9aad87d3608e34991b8743e9a
YARNGASM: Episode 278 - "Living On the Edge" [BicN7eyA2U4].mkv

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YARNGASM: Episode 281 - "There's Been Spinning" [066xjOf4DhM].mkv
```

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